

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D6.4 – Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 2

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	The D6.4 Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 2, presents the initial efforts of UP2030 to disseminate the activities conducted and raise awareness regarding the project. The document includes all the activities performed in the first fifteen months of UP2030, the materials produced, the tools utilized to increase the visibility of the project, and the evaluation of their progress.			

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Executive summary

This deliverable offers a comprehensive overview of the progress made in the implementation of the dissemination and communication (D&C) strategy outlined in D6.1 “Dissemination and Communication Strategy 1” and D6.2 “Dissemination and Communication Strategy 2”. Covering the period from M7 to M16 of the project, it is a continuation of D6.3 “Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 1”. Therefore, it has a similar structure and aims to provide a detailed account of the D&C activities undertaken, the communication channels utilized and the achieved outcomes.

Included in this report are the objectives of the activities, details of promotional tools and materials developed, updates on the project website and social media presence, a thorough presentation of individual dissemination actions performed by the consortium partners and an assessment of performance of all actions against targeted KPIs.

Content Alignment with other UP2030 Deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages’ (WPs) structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with WP1 MANAGE - Project Management, WP2 UP-DATING - Understanding cities’ and stakeholders’ needs for upgrading, and co-designing visions of urban transformations , WP3 UP-SKILLING - Empowering the city’s stakeholder ecosystem to co-develop urban planning and design enabled transformation pathways, WP4 UP-GRADING - Piloting and demonstrating, WP5 UP-SCALING - Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making and WP6 UP-TAKING - Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Sustainability of UP2030, as it contains communication and dissemination activities carried out by partners leading or contributing to tasks of WP6. The following table lists the deliverables which provided input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
D6.1 Dissemination & Communication Strategy 1	D6.4 Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 2
D6.2 Dissemination & Communication Strategy 2	D6.5 Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 3
D6.3 Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 1	D6.12 Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s Platform
D1.7 Security Privacy and Ethics Handbook	

The target groups for this deliverable primarily include the coordination team and the consortium partners involved in the implementation of the project. They are the main beneficiaries of this content as it provides them with an analytical but comprehensive overview of the D&C actions and their impact performed by the consortium between M7 to M16. Once finalized, the content will be available to partners through the project’s SharePoint and to the public through the project’s website.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
ADELPHI	ADELPHI RESEARCH GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AQUATEC	AQUATEC PROYECTOS PARA EL SECTOR DEL AGUA SA
Belfast	Belfast City Council
BH	BURO HAPPOLD GMBH
BIO- CiVo	Citizen Voices in Biodiversity
Budapest	BUDAPEST FOVAROS ONKORMANYZATA
CCC	CLIMATE NEUTRAL CITY CONTRACTS
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS
CETAQUA	CETAQUA, CENTRO TECNOLOGICO DEL AGUA, FUNDACION PRIVADA
CIRCE	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS
CML	Capital Market Line
CmC	Citizens Meets Climate
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DC	DESIGN CLIPS IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA
DELTARES	STICHTING DELTARES
DRAXIS	DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL SA
DreVen	DREVEN SRL
DSIG	Data Steward Interest Group
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH

EU	European Union
EURESFO	European Urban Resilience Forum
Fraunhofer	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV
GGGI	GLOBAL GREEN GROWTH INSTITUTE
Granollers	AJUNTAMENT DE GRANOLLERS
GreenAdapt	GREENADAPT GESELLSCHAFT FUER KLIMAAANPASSUNG MBH
GUNAM	ODTU GUNES ENERJISI UYGULAMA VE ARA STIRMA MERKEZI
ICA	I-CATALIST SL
ICLEI	ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)
IFEU	Institute for Energy and Environmental Research
ISOCARP	STICHTING ISOCARP INSTITUTE CENTER OF URBAN EXCELLENCE
Istanbul	Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality (IMM)
K3Y	K3Y
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIF	PRAVO I INTERNET FOUNDATION
LINKS	FONDAZIONE LINKS - LEADING INNOVATION & KNOWLEDGE FOR SOCIETY
LISBOA	LISBOA E-NOVA - AGENCIA DE ENERGIA E AMBIENTE DE LISBOA
LisbonTable 16	CAMARA MUNICIPAL DE LISBOA (Lisbon Municipality)
LNEC	LABORATORIO NACIONAL DE ENGENHARIA CIVIL
DCCs	Digital Currency Communities
MAG	MAGGIOLI SPA
MDAT	ANAPTYXIAKI MEIZONOS ASTIKIS THESSALONIKIS AE - ANAPTYXIAKOS ORGANISMOS TOPIKIS AUTODIOIKISIS
METU	MIDDLE EAST TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

MfC	MAPPING FOR CHANGE CIC
Milan	COMUNE DI MILANO (Municipality of Milan)
MIP4Adapt	Mission Implementation Platform
Muenster	STADT MUNSTER (Municipality of Münster)
Mx	Month x
NYIT	New York Institute of Technology
Rcities	STICHTING GLOBAL RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK
RDA-NL	Research Data Alliance NL
Rotterdam	GEMEENTE ROTTERDAM (City of Rotterdam)
T	Task
Thessaloniki	DIMOS THESSALONIKIS (City of Thessaloniki)
TSPA	STELLMACH THOMAS
TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
UCAM	THE CHANCELLOR MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE
UCCRN	URBAN CLIMATE CHANGE RESEARCH NETWORK - EUROPEAN HUB APS
UDCW	URBAN DESIGN CLIMATE WORKSHOP
UIC	UNIVERSITAT INTERNACIONAL DE CATALUNYA
UNINA	UNIVERSITY OF NAPLES FEDERICO II
UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA
USTUTT	UNIVERSITY OF STUTTGART
VM	VESELA MOTIKA D.O.O. ZA PROIZVODNJU TRGOVINU I USLUGE
VUB	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL
WP	Work package
Zagreb	GRAD ZAGREB

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this document is to provide a detailed report of the implementation and progress of all dissemination and communication (D&C) actions within the UP2030 project framework, as initially presented in Deliverable 6.1 (D6.1) D6.1 “Dissemination and Communication strategy 1” and D.6.2 “Dissemination and Communication strategy 2” submitted in M3 and M15 respectively. It encompasses comprehensive details to streamline the execution and oversight of diverse tasks and activities associated with the project's D&C objectives from M7 to M16. Additionally, it provides insights into the channels utilized thus far, monitoring procedures, communication policies, and other pertinent information essential for facilitating efficient and continuous cooperation and information exchange among partners.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: Describing the purpose, the scope of the document and its structure.
- ❖ Section 2 – Dissemination and Communication Activities Performed from M7 to M16: Presenting the dissemination activities performed from M7 to M16 including consortium partners' individual dissemination actions.
- ❖ Section 3– Dissemination Activities: Referring to workshops and events, individual dissemination activities, joint activities with relevant initiatives and publications.
- ❖ Section 4 – Communication Tools and Activities: Referring to the project website, social media presence, newsletters, blog posts, press releases and press kit.
- ❖ Section 5 – Dissemination and Communication Monitoring: Presenting the monitoring files for dissemination and communication activities and related indicators.
- ❖ Section 6 – Dissemination and Communication Planned Activities.
- ❖ Section 7 – Conclusions.

2 Dissemination and Communication Activities Performed from M7 to M16

The period between the first report in D6.1 (M6- June 2023) and M16 (April 2024) has seen the following activities concisely implemented:

- Constant update of the website's content
- Constant update of social media accounts
- Launch of the blog page of the website (M10)
- Scientific and technical publications
- Publication of newsletters
- Increase of the visibility of UP2030 – according to KPIs
- Participation and organization of workshops and events
- Establishment of new synergies with relevant projects and initiatives

The activities mentioned above will undergo deeper analysis in the forthcoming sections of this deliverable.

3 Dissemination Activities

In D6.3 “Dissemination and Communication activities and their impact 1”, dissemination activities are carried out throughout UP2030's duration to maximize project result impact. They are strategically planned and detailed in D6.1 and D6.2. From M7 to M16, a comprehensive array of activities was diligently undertaken, contributing to the project's advancement and efficacy. These initiatives encompassed a spectrum of endeavors aimed at enhancing project visibility, showcasing its progress and innovative potential, and elucidating its broader societal implications to the public.

3.1 Workshops and Events

Between M7 and M16, the project partners consistently engaged in a series of activities aimed at advancing the project's objectives. These efforts included the continuation of workshops and events, aligned with the needs assessment and developing implementation roadmaps. The focus remained primarily on the pilot cities participating in UP2030. In addition, consortium partners participated in multiple conferences, forums, and community events where they articulated the project's objectives and scope and fostered engagement with stakeholders.

The Table 1 below provides an overview of all events, presented on a timeline that includes the date, location, event title, event websites, and participating partners, listing the events in chronological order.

Annex 1 can be found organized and grouped **by date**, providing comprehensive details for each workshop, conference community event and forum. This annex features event titles, dates, locations, event websites, and information on dissemination through social media (if applicable):

Table 1 Event List

Date	Location	Event	Event website link	Partner
15/06/2023	Muenster, Germany	Climate City Forum	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/stadtforum	Muenster
18/07/2023 - 22/07/2023	Santander, Spain	NetZeroCities Summer School	https://netzerocities.eu/2023/08/01/netzerocities-summer-schools-helping-cities-accelerate-their-climate-transition/	Muenster, Lisbon
30/08/2023 - 31/08/2023	Puerto Varas, Chile	Los Lagos Vision Sostenible	N/A	Fraunhofer
05/09/2023 - 06/09/2023	Punta Arenas, Chile	Magallanes Visión Sostenible	N/A	Fraunhofer

06/09/2023 - 08/09/2023	Goyang, South Korea	World Smart Cities Expo	https://www.worldsmartcityexpo.com/fairDash.do?hl=ENG	Fraunhofer
20/09/2023 - 21/09/2023	Benicàssim, Castellón, Spain	Benicàssim Conference	https://baio.webs.upv.es/	UPV
26/09/2023	Lisbon, Portugal	"Urban Environments and Human Health in Lisbon" Conference	Instituto de Saúde Ambiental (ulisboa.pt)	LNEC, Lisbon
28/09/2023	Barcelona, Spain	ARSINOE Exploitation Workshop: Paving the Path to Climate Resilience	www.arsinoe-project.eu	Lisbon
28/09/2023	Lisbon, Portugal	Visit/work Meeting with the Viena Municipality	N/A	Lisbon
02/10/2023 - 06/10/2023	Montréal, Canada (Hybrid)	Adaptation Futures 2023	https://adaptationfutures.com/	UCCRN
04/10/2023 - 06/10/2023	Seville, Spain	Urban Mobility Days	Urban Mobility Days 2023 - European Commission (europa.eu)	Fraunhofer
05/10/2023	Tallinn, Estonia	European Green Capital & European Green Leaf Ceremony 2025	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/european-green-capital-european-green-leaf-ceremony	Lisbon
12/10/2023	Lisbon, Portugal	Smart Cities Summit 2023	https://portugalsmartcities.fil.pt/	Lisbon
12/10/2023	Brussels, Belgium	European Week of Regions and Cities	Achieving Climate Neutral Cities through the Regeneration of Historic Urban Areas European Week of Regions and Cities (europa.eu)	Lisbon

17/10/2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	Workshop UP2030 Adaptive Pathways	https://mdat.gr/2024/04/08/	MDAT
17/10/2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	UP2030 Spatial Assessment Workshop Thessaloniki	N/A	MDAT
18/10/2023	Lisbon, Portugal	Life Lungs 2nd Technical Meeting - The role of cities in combating climate change"	N/A	Lisbon
18/10/2023	Barcelona, Spain	Cities fighting against climate emergency. Keys to a just transition.	https://www.institutmetropoli.cat/ca/noticias/ciutats-enfront-emergencia-climatica-jornada/	Granollers
18/10/2023-20/10/2023	Cascais, Portugal	EURESFO	N/A	LNEC
18/10/2023-20/10/2023	Cascais, Portugal	EURESFO: "Designing Resilient, Climate-Neutral Cities: District-focused Innovations"	https://urbanresiliencforum.eu/	Rcities, Rotterdam
20/10/2023	Lisbon, Portugal	Visit/work Meeting with the Lathi Municipality	N/A	Lisbon
21/10/2023 - 27/10/2023	Muenster, Germany	Climate City Week	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/rueckblick-klimastadt-woche	Muenster
25/10/2023 - 27/10/2023	Prato, Italy	Major Cities of Europe Annual Conference 2023	https://majorcities.eu/conferences/2023-prato/	MAG
26/10/2023-27/10/2023	Barcelona, Spain	Benchmarking Workshop	N/A	BH

27/10/2023	Seoul, South Korea & online via Zoom	Global Green Growth Week	https://globalgreengrowthweek.gggi.org/	GGGI
27/10/2023	Muenster, Germany	KlimaBarCamp (part of the Climate Week)	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/rueckblick-klimastadt-woche	Muenster
07/11/2023 - 08/11/2023	Alcoy, Spain	Alcoy Artificial Intelligence & Optimization workshop	https://alcoytech.webs.upv.es/	UPV
09/11/2023	Lisbon, Portugal	Visit/work Meeting with District 6 of the Bucharest Municipality	N/A	Lisbon
13/11/2023 - 15/11/2023	LNEC, Lisbon, Portugal	UP2030 General Assembly	N/A	ALL
20/11/2023 - 23/11/2023	LNEC, Lisbon, Portugal	Course on Integrating Water in Urban Planning Nature-based Solutions	N/A	LNEC
21/11/2023	Virtual Event	Tools for the Greenhouse Gas-neutral Municipality: Climate Fund	www.klimaschutz.de/agentur	Muenster
22/11/2023	Barcelona, Spain	Final Meeting and Conference of Climatubers (Erasmus+ Project)	https://epale.ec.europa.eu/en/content/climatubers-final-conference	Granollers
05/12/2023	Delft, Netherlands & online	Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design	https://just-city.org/conferences/practice/	UCCRN, Rotterdam, Budapest

08/01 /2024 - 12/01 /2024	Rotterdam, Netherlands	Workshop Citizen Voices in Biodiversity (Workshop in Dies Natalis)	https://www.tudelft.nl/en/2023/bk/join-the-dies-delta-week-from-8-12-january	TUD
17/01/2024	Budapest, Hungary	1st Visioning Workshop Budapest	N/A	Budapest
24/01/2024	Granollers, Spain	Workshop #2: Vision on “Neutral neighborhoods in Granollers, habitable and desirable”	https://www.granollers.cat/ajuntament/up2030	Granollers
27/01/ 2024	Utrecht, Netherlands	Blood, Sweat & Tears: Learnings from Citizen Voice, a bottom-up open research project (Teaming Up Across Domains)	https://tdcc.nl/evenementen/teaming-up-across-domains/	TUD
27/01/2024	Delft, Netherlands	Empowering Citizen Participation in Climate Action with Digital Platforms	https://www.tudelft.nl/evenementen/2024/open-science/empowering-citizen-participation-in-climate-action-with-digital-platforms	TUD
06/02/2024 & 29/02/2024	Virtual Event	Mission Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt)	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/the-mission/about-mip4adapt	Granollers
28/02/2024	Palácio Galveias, Lisbon, Portugal	Vision Workshop #Rethink Carbon Neutrality and Climate Resilience	N/A	Lisbon
28/02/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	UP2030 StepUPLxALL	N/A	LNEC

28/02/2024	Muenster, Germany	Muenster Climate City Contract Event	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/klimastadtvertrag	Muenster
06/03/2024 - 12/06/2024	Muenster, Germany	4th KlimaTraining	N/A	Muenster
12/03/2024	Budapest, Hungary	Healthy Streets© Conference	N/A	Budapest
12/03/2024	Thessaloniki, Greece	UP2030 Vision Workshop Thessaloniki	https://mdat.gr/2024/03/14/	MDAT
14/03/2024	Muenster, Germany	Vision Workshop	N/A	BH
14/03/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	Procura+ Conference	https://conference.procuraplus.org/study-visits	Lisbon
18/03/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	Workshop “Nature-Based Solutions – Climate Responses in Lisbon”	N/A	Lisbon
18/03/2024-24/03/2024	Naples, Italy	UDCW (Urban Design Climate Workshop)	https://www.uccrn.edu/cation/napoli-udcw/	UCCRN
20/03/2024	Milan, Italy	2nd Visioning Workshop	N/A	LINKS
23/03/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	Planet Festival 2024 in Alvalade	https://www.lisboa.pt/atualidade/noticias/detalhe/hora-do-planeta-celebrada-com-arraial/	Lisbon
20/03/2024 - 21/03/2024	Metz, France	Franco-German Future Center, Resonance Room on the Topic of Energy Sufficiency	https://df-zukunftswerk.eu/aktuelles	Muenster
27/03/2024	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	UCCRN Expert Meeting - G20 side event	https://uccrn.ei.columbia.edu/news/uccrn-climate-change-and-cities-expert-meeting	UCCRN

25/3/2024 - 5/4/2024	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	UDCW Rio de Janeiro	https://www.uccrn.edu/cation/rio-de-janeiro-6th-multiplier/	TUD
25/3/2024 - 5/4/2024	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	UCCRN_edu Multiplier Event Rio de Janeiro	https://www.uccrn.edu/cation/rio-de-janeiro-6th-multiplier/	UCCRN, DELTARES, TUD
March, April 2024	Lisbon, Portugal	Community Event - Urban Art Collective Painting - Mural	N/A	Lisbon
03/04/2024	Granollers, Spain	Adaptive Pathways Workshop	N/A	Granollers
11/04/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	6º Encontro UniverCidades 2024: Ideias para Lisboa, Centro de Informação Urbana de Lisboa (CIUL)	https://www.belasartes.lisboa.pt/encontro-univercidades-ideias-para-lisboa-2/	Lisbon
16/04/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	UP2030 Pilot Guided Visit (Alvalade Route)	https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=16c65dd94f604f49ab5a17fc22e7841b	Lisbon
30/04/2024	Granollers, Spain	Cultural diversity sessions	N/A	Granollers

3.2 Upcoming Workshops and Events

Table 2 provides a brief outline of the forthcoming events and workshops in which project partners may engage or organize in the upcoming months. The table presents a “living” internal; document that is enriched and updated monthly. The detailed reporting will feature in D6.5 “Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 3” which is expected by M36.

Table 2 Individual Upcoming events

Event	Date and Venue	Relevant URL (event website)	Partner(s) planning to participate
Urban Futures 2024	5-7 June 2024 Rotterdam, Netherlands	https://urban-future.org/	RCITIES

EURESFO	26-28 June 2024 Valencia, Spain	https://urbanresilienceforum.eu/	N/A
Changing Cities Conference	24-28 June 2024 Rhodes, Greece	N/A	THESSALONIKI
AESOP	8-11 July 2024 Paris France	https://aesop-planning.eu	METU & GUNAM
Climate Change Congress	29-31 July 2024 Lisbon, Portugal	https://www.greenenergy-europe.eu	N/A
EU PVSEC	23-27 September 2024 Vienna, Austria	https://www.eupvsec.org/	METU & GUNAM
Milan Green Week	26-29 September 2024 Milan, Italy	https://www.comune.milano.it	MILAN
Global Green Growth Week	21-25 October 2024 Cali, Colombia	N/A	GGGI
Association of European Schools of Planning Conference	N/A	N/A	ISTANBUL METROPOLITAN MUNICIPALITY
Smart City Expo World Congress	5-7 November 2024 Barcelona, Spain	https://www.smartcityexpo.com/	DREVEN/ RCITIES
World Urban Forum	4-8 November 2024 Cairo, Egypt	WUF12 WUF (unhabitat.org)	TUD / Fraunhofer

3.3 Individual Dissemination Activities

Table 3 presents an overview of the individual dissemination activities performed by partners between M7 to M16 including the events and workshops portrayed in detail in section 3.1, as well as, the social

media posts, press releases and other actions. The letter “X” indicates activity of the partner on the specific domain.

Table 3 Individual Dissemination Activities

Partner Name	Events	Workshops	Social Media LinkedIn	Social Media X	Social Media FB/Instagram	Web site	Press release	Other D&C
ADELPHI						X		
ACUATEC			X	X				X
BH		X	X				X	
Budapest	X	X						
CERTH								
CETAQUA			X	X				
CIRCE			X	X				
DC			X					
DELTARES		X						
ETH			X					
Fraunhofer	X		X					
GGGI	X		X			X		
Granollers	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
GUNAM								
ISOCARP			X					X
Istanbul			X	X				
K3Y			X	X	X	X	X	
LIF						X		
LINKS		X	X					

Partner Name	Events	Workshops	Social Media LinkedIn	Social Media X	Social Media FB/Instagram	Web site	Press release	Other D&C
Lisbon	X	X		X	X		X	
LNEC	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
MAG	X							
MDAT		X	X	X	X			
METU			X	X			X	
MfC			X	X		X		
Milan			X			X		
Munster	X				X			
Rcities	X		X					
Rotterdam	X		X	X	X	X		
Thessaloniki					X			
TSPA			X	X	X	X		
TUD		X	X		X			
UCCRN	X	X	X		X			
UPV	X							

3.4 Joint Activities with the Mission and Relevant Initiatives

UP2030 consortium is focused on maximizing the impact of the project activities and in this framework is enclosed the alignment with the Mission and related projects (eg. Smart Cities Marketplace, Scalable Cities etc.). An initial report of the relative activities was presented in D6.3.

Within Task 6.4 (T6.4) “Collaboration with the Mission and related projects activities”, ICLEI prepared a roadmap: Collaboration with the Mission and related projects. This roadmap is a guiding document to initiate and strengthen the collaboration between the Cities Mission, NetZeroCities, and the related Mission projects (UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH and RE-VALUE) (UP2030, 2024). ICLEI has developed this document to outline the main objectives and the key activities to achieve cross-sectorial collaboration among the above-mentioned projects and initiatives of the Cities Mission.

The figure below - included in the Roadmap - provides a summary of the framework outlining the main objectives of these activities, which are to enhance dissemination and identify cross-cutting themes, and to raise awareness of the project to the Mission and the key players and actors involved in this context. (UP2030, 2024)

Source: ICLEI

Figure 1 UP2030 mission and collaboration structure

During this period, UP2030 joined its efforts with the cluster projects and online meetings among the coordinators of these projects and the communication leaders were held. The cluster projects participated in the 10th anniversary of the EURESFO that took place on the 18th and 19th of October in Cascais. For the upcoming months, the joint representation of the cluster projects in events (e.g. EURESFO, Smart Cities Expo) is planned.

In D6.2, specifically in section 2.3 “Synergies with Mission and collaboration with related projects” the key activities of collaboration with relevant initiatives are described. (UP2030, 2024) More detailed information will be provided in the D6.10 “Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1”, which will be delivered by the end of M18 and is led by ICLEI.

3.5 Publications

The UP2030 project has set high standards for publications, aiming for 30 scientific and 20 technical outputs as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) respectively. A project group has been formed to lead the publication strategy, coordinated by DreVen and involving ISOCARP, UIC, and the Task Force of Dissemination. Additionally, monthly meetings have been established to coordinate efforts towards achieving the expected publications both quantitatively and qualitatively, with participants including UCCRN, TU DELFT, UCAM, and others. So far, the following publications have been accomplished:

Table 4 Submitted Publications.

Partner	Publication Title	Date of Publication	Type of Publication	URL link (if any)
UPV	Analyzing Key Performance Indicators for Mobility Logistics in Smart and Sustainable Cities: A Case Study Centered on Barcelona	16 October 2023	Scientific	https://www.mdpi.com/2305-6290/7/4/75
UPV	Promoting Energy Efficiency and Emissions Reduction in Urban Areas with Key Performance Indicators and Data Analytics	22 October 2023	Scientific	https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/16/20/7195
METU & GUNAM	Transfer Learning-Based Prediction of Heating Energy Consumption Using Urban Building Energy Models (UBEM)	N/A	Scientific	https://3dgeoinfoeg-ice.webs.uvigo.es/eg-ice
TUD	Book of Abstracts Symposium Spatial Planning in Practice	N/A	Scientific	https://just-city.org/conferences/practice/

The UP2030 project adopted an open-access dissemination policy for the published research work via Zenodo, an established online European scientific repository that is fully integrated with OpenAIRE. A detailed description of Zenodo's policies regarding the handling of the data and usage of the service is found [here](#). DreVen created an account for the project in M16 (April 2024) and the UP2030 community will host all the open-access published research work. Furthermore, the publications are hosted on the [dedicated page](#) of the project website.

At the beginning of the second year of the project, DreVen requested all partners to provide information regarding the number of publications they intend to produce, the topics they will cover, and their planned timelines. This was aimed at better coordinating these efforts by the project group. Based on this information, discussions were held, leading to the decision that in addition to individual partner publications, the project will also proceed with the release of two special issues. The first will be led by partner TUD and will focus on spatial justice. The second will be led by partner UIC and will address barriers.

4 Communication Tools and Activities

Communication activities are implemented through a variety of channels and tools, which are selected according to the preferences and maximum expected impact of each target audience. Factors that are taken into consideration of selecting them appropriately are people's knowledge of technological means and their technical skills, as well as their interests, i.e. younger audiences are more likely to be attached to their phones and use social media channels than older people.¹

The main tools and channels used for the communication of the project are the UP2030 website, the social media accounts on LinkedIn and X, the YouTube channel of UP2030, newsletters, press releases and blog posts.

4.1 Project Website

The website of the UP2030 project, located at <https://up2030-he.eu/>, serves as a valuable resource for accessing information, updates and resources related to the project's initiatives and progress.

Figure 2 UP2030 website

4.1.1 Project Website Content

The content of the UP2030 website undergoes continuous updates, ensuring that visitors have access to the latest news and project outcomes. In comparison to the previous report in D6.3, significant enhancements have been made, including the launch of the UP2030 blog page on the website available [here](#).

¹ Smith, A., Anderson, M. (2018). Social Media Use in 2018. Pew Research Center. Available at: <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2018/03/01/social-media-use-in-2018/> [Accessed 20.11.23]

Figure 3 UP2030 Blog page

Additionally, the "News & Events" page is constantly refreshed with relevant articles, and these are presented on the homepage of the website as well to attract the visitors' attention. Below are presented the articles uploaded to this page by M16.

- [Introduction to UP2030 Project](#)
- [UP2030 in the 10th Edition of the European Urban Resilience Forum](#)
- [Exploring Urban Mobility Innovation at Urban Mobility Days 2023](#)
- [Highlights from UP2030's 1st General Assembly in Lisbon](#)
- [The Symposium 'Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design](#)
- [UP2030 in Major Cities of Europe Annual Conference](#)
- [2nd workshop of the UP2030 project in Granollers](#)
- [UP2030 project workshop in Budapest](#)

Figure 4 UP2030 News & Events page

Moreover, the public UP2030 deliverables have been added to their respective page (<https://up2030-he.eu/library-deliverables/>), enriching the website's resources and providing comprehensive information on the project's developments.

Figure 5 UP2030 Deliverables page

On [the Communication Kit page](#) of the UP2030 website, all relevant materials created thus far have been added and are available for viewing and download. Specifically:

- UP2030 logo
- UP2030 logo v2
- UP2030 logo white
- UP2030 Brochure
- UP2030 Presentation
- UP2030 Poster
- UP2030 Newsletter #1
- UP2030 Newsletter #2

Figure 6 UP2030 Communication kit page

The content of the UP2030 website will continue to be updated regularly to ensure it encompasses all necessary and up-to-date information regarding the project.

4.1.2 [Project Website Performance](#)

The performance of the UP2030 website from M6 to M16 demonstrates its significance as one of the primary channels for enhancing the project's impact among wider audiences. Throughout this period, the website has consistently served as a crucial platform for disseminating information, engaging stakeholders and promoting project achievements. The overall performance of the website in the last ten months is presented in the figure below (Figure 7).

Figure 7 UP2030 website's performance from M6 to M16

During the initial six months, the website garnered 1 100 users – as reported in D6.3. Impressively, over the subsequent ten months, it saw a significant increase, attracting an additional 4.000 new users. This substantial growth underscores the expanding reach and effectiveness of the website as a key platform for disseminating information and engaging with stakeholders over time.

4.2 Social Media Presence

The UP2030 project actively maintains [LinkedIn](#) and [X](#) accounts, since the third month of the project, recognizing the crucial role of social media in disseminating information. Weekly updates on these platforms are managed by DreVen, focusing on highlighting the project's ongoing activities for the respective week. DreVen collaborates with partners to ensure that the content accurately reflects their contributions and efforts within the UP2030 project activities. The social media accounts of the project follow relevant initiatives and accounts that may act as ambassadors of UP2030 in social media and consequently contribute to its dissemination.

4.2.1 Social Media Performance

From M7 to M16, the [UP2030 LinkedIn page](#) experienced a notable increase in followers, rising by 389 to reach a total of 779 followers. During this eleventh-month period, the page also received 1616 page views and had 663 unique visitors, as illustrated in the figures below.

Figure 8 UP2030 LinkedIn page followers metrics (M7-M16)

Figure 9 UP2030 LinkedIn page Views

The X account of UP2030 has accumulated 2005 impressions from M6 to M16. Analytics are presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10 UP2030 X account analytics

Table 5 Individual Partners Facebook & Instagram posts.

Facebook & Instagram			
Account	Date	Engagement	Link
TSPA	17/11/2023	0 reactions,	https://www.facebook.com/ttssppaa
TSPA	28/09/2023	2 likes	https://www.facebook.com/ttssppaa
Lisbon	26/09/2023	34 reactions	https://www.facebook.com/LisboaAmbiente/posts
Lisbon	27/11/2023	34 reactions	https://www.instagram.com/p/COLqcnkM21Z/
Lisbon	27/11/2023	34 Info reactions	https://www.facebook.com/LisboaAmbiente/posts
Lisbon	28/02/2024	N/A yet	https://www.facebook.com/LisboaAmbiente/posts
Lisbon	01/03/2024	N/A yet	https://www.instagram.com/p/C390N27NQ2h
Lisbon	17/04/2024	N/A yet	https://www.instagram.com/reel/
Lisbon	22/03/2024	N/A yet	O arraial da Hora do Planeta... - Câmara Municipal de Lisboa
LNEC	13/10/2023	N/A	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=823241013139873&set=a.467004535430191
LNEC	9/06/2023	N/A	https://www.instagram.com/p/CtRYDOOoK2b/?igshid=NmJiYWZiY2E0Mg==
MDAT	17/11/2023	16 reactions	https://www.facebook.com/mdaThessaloniki/posts
MDAT	17/10/2023	15 reactions	https://www.facebook.com/mdaThessaloniki/posts
MDAT	05/04/2024	35 reactions	https://www.facebook.com/mdaThessaloniki/posts
Irene Tsakiridou / MDAT	05/04/2024	12 reactions	https://www.instagram.com/p/C5YO4b0oYwN2W63b4H0m-GhKSDP0SKR8kAzvBM0/
MDAT	02/04/2024	12 reactions	https://www.facebook.com/mdaThessaloniki/posts
Thessaloniki	01/04/2024	17 reactions	https://www.facebook.com/resilientThess/posts

MDAT	17/11/2023	16 reactions	https://www.facebook.com/mdaThessaloniki/posts
MDAT	17/10/2023	15 reactions	https://www.facebook.com/mdaThessaloniki/posts
K3Y	24/02/23	Impressions: 45, Reach: 27, Engagement: 6	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
K3Y	02/06/23	Impressions: 33, Reach: 17, Engagement: 3	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
K3Y	15/11/2023	Impressions: 16, Reach: 10, Engagement: 1	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
K3Y	24/11/2023	Impressions: 23, Reach: 16, Engagement: 3	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
K3Y	12/12/2023	Impressions: 18, Reach: 12, Engagement: 3	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
K3Y	11/01/2024	Impressions: 19, Reach: 11, Engagement: 4	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
K3Y	24/01/2024	Impressions: 21, Reach: 13, Engagement: 4	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
K3Y	31/01/2024	Impressions: 17 Reach: 9, Engagement: 4	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
K3Y	08/04/2024	Impressions: 11 Reach: 11, Engagement: 2	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=...
Munster	N/A	N/A	https://www.facebook.com/stadt.muenster/?locale=de_DE
Gutes Morgen Münster / Munster	17/05/2023	1 reaction	https://www.facebook.com/gutesmorgenmunster/
Unser Klima 2030/ Munster	4/10/23 6/10/23 2 X 9/10/23 11/10/23 12/10/23	25 190 467 25 138	https://www.instagram.com/unserklima2030/?hl=de

		reactions (Total: 845 reactions)	
Munster	N/A	N/A	https://www.facebook.com/stadt.muenster
@centrefor thejustcity/ TUD	27/11/23	Reach: 211 Impressions: 239	https://www.instagram.com/p/C0KUv2dsqVd/
UCCRN EDU	04/04/24	12 likes, 1 comment	https://www.instagram.com/reel
UCCRN EDU	30/03/24	27 reactions, 6 comments	https://www.instagram.com/reelNg%3D%3D
UCCRN EDU	25/03/24	5 reactions	https://www.instagram.com/p/C48L_3cMsRv
UCCRN EDU	23/03/24	9 reactions	https://www.instagram.com/p/C43MKZxsmXQ
UCCRN EDU	19/03/24	9 reactions	https://www.instagram.com/uccrneducation/p/C4siZ4Ys4YV/

Table 6 Individual Partners LinkedIn posts.

LinkedIn			
Account	Date	Engagement	Link
TSPA	17/11/2023	14 reactions 1 repost	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
TSPA	28/09/2023	32 reactions, 3 reposts	https://www.linkedin.com/feed
UCCRN EDU	05/10/23	11 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/theo-uccrn-education
UCCRN EDU	15/04/24	12 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update https://www.linkedin.com/posts/uccrn-education
UCCRN EDU	06/04/24	11 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
UCCRN EDU	25/03/24	1 reaction	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
UCCRN EDU	23/03/24	2 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
UCCRN EDU	19/03/24	4 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update

Irene Tsakiridou / MDAT	18/12/2023	23 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Irene Tsakiridou / MDAT	15/11/2023	17 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Irene Tsakiridou / MDAT	15/11/2023	17 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Virgínia Domingo Reig / Granollers	28/11/23	1 reaction 0 shares	Repost of: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Virgínia Domingo Reig / Granollers	21/11/23	1 reaction 0 shares	Repost of: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/up2030
Judit Tarradellas / Granollers	28/11/23	1 reaction 0 shares	Repost of: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Judit Tarradellas / Granollers	21/11/23	1 reaction 0 share	https://www.linkedin.com/posts
Judit Tarradellas / Granollers	21/11/23	1 reaction 0 share	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/up2030
Judit Tarradellas / Granollers	11/11/23	1 reaction 0 share	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/up2030
Icatalist and repost by Granollers' team	25/01/24	48 reactions, 1 repost, 1 comment	Repost of: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
UP2030HE and repost by Granollers' team	25/01/24	44 reactions, 4 reposts	Repost of: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Montse Martínez /	29/04/2023	34 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update

Aquatec's researcher			
Montse Martínez / Aquatec's researcher	08/06/2023	1 reaction	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Catalina Diaz / Fraunhofer	15/10/23	79 reactions 7 comments	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/catalina-diaz
Fraunhofer	15/12/23	20 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/fraunhofer
GUNAM	25/11/2023	67 reactions, 5 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtu
GUNAM	12/11/2023	59 reactions, 2 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtu-gunam
GUNAM	20/06/2023	71 reactions, 5 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtu
GUNAM	24/08/2023	49 reactions, 2 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtu
İpek Gürsel Dino - GUNAM	18/10/2023	131 reactions, 1 share	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ipek-gursel
GUNAM & Istanbul	18/12/2023	Shared while filling out this form	https://www.linkedin.com/posts
GUNAM & METU	27/03/2024	16 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtu
GUNAM & METU & Istanbul	17/03/2024	17 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtu-
GUNAM	17/01/2024	9 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtu
GUNAM & METU & Istanbul	01/2024	38 reactions, 5 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtu
K3Y	24/02/23	Unique Impressions: 36, Engagements: 15	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7034882663257681920
K3Y	23/03/23	Unique Impressions: 30, Engagements: 9	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7044630827099467776
K3Y	12/04/23	Unique Impressions: 33, Engagements: 7	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7051841651694075906

K3Y	28/04/23	Unique Impressions: 28, Engagements: 5	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057671448567414784
K3Y	26/05/23	Unique Impressions: 33, Engagements: 19	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7067790393202872320
K3Y	02/06/23	Unique Impressions: 42, Engagements: 5	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7070402491753861120
K3Y	07/06/2023	Unique Impressions: 33, Engagements: 6	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072229554878111744
K3Y	16/06/2023	Unique Impressions: 38, Engagements: 4	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7075447223223787520
K3Y	05/07/2023	Unique Impressions: 36, Engagements: 12	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7082322422988779520
K3Y	12/07/2023	Unique Impressions: 32, Engagements: 3	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7084840423965286400
K3Y	10/08/2023	Unique Impressions: 46, Engagements: 4	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7095325286224846848
K3Y	15/11/2023	Unique Impressions: 34, Engagements: 3	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130593601398464512
K3Y	24/11/2023	Unique Impressions: 85, Engagements: 34	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133753913857425410
K3Y	12/12/2023	Unique Impressions: 39, Engagements: 3	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7140370461871304704
K3Y	11/01/2024	Unique Impressions: 14, Engagements: 4	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7151191353568223233
K3Y	24/01/2024	Unique Impressions: 104, Engagements: 8	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7155864931282608129
K3Y	31/01/2024	Unique Impressions: 25, Engagements: 3	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7158440790287921154
K3Y	06/02/2024	Unique Impressions: 49, Engagements: 10	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7160593047355809792
K3Y	06/03/2024	Unique Impressions: 95, Engagements: 14	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171093131914932225
K3Y	08/04/2024	Unique Impressions: 33, Engagements: 3	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7183053139976019968
Eduardo Di Gangi / LINKS	22/03/2024	Total from reposts: 53 reactions - 4 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/up2030

UP2030 HE/LINKS	11/04/2024	22 reactions – 3 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts
Maria Adriana Cardoso / LNEC researcher	4/2024	Repost Mission Climate-Neutral Smart Cities, Lisbon and Thessaloniki	https://www.linkedin.com/feed
Maria Adriana Cardoso / LNEC researcher	3/2024	Repost Newsletter #2	https://www.linkedin.com/in/maria-adriana-cardoso
Maria Adriana Cardoso / LNEC researcher	2/2024	Repost 2nd workshop Lisbon	https://www.linkedin.com/in/maria-adriana
Maria Adriana Cardoso / LNEC researcher	January 2024	Repost UP2030 Happy New Year	https://www.linkedin.com/in/maria-adriana
Roberto Rocco / TUD	16/04/24	Impressions: +10000	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/roberto
Hugo Lopez / TUD	04/24	Impressions: +1000	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/iamhug
GGGI	15/11/2023	11 likes	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130510306417475586
GGGI	24/10/2023	11 Likes, 3 reposts	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122515897981808641
GGGI	30/01/2024	11 Likes, 1 Repost	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7158135397871419392
GGGI	28/03/2024	3 Likes	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7179111867070464002
BH	24/05/2023	81 reactions, 5 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/buro
Felicitas Leithner / BH	10/2023	38 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/activity

Peter Scheibstock / BH	11/2023	71 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts
Jill Theobald / BH	26/04/2024	26 reactions, 1 share	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/jill-theobald
Sebastian Seelig / BH	26/04/2024	6 likes	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/sebastian
DC	20/03/2024	Reposts: 1 Reactions: 8	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/designclips
ETH	28/02/2024	8 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ceaethz
Milan	21/03/2024	N/A	https://www.linkedin.com/posts
MfC	13/12/2023	N/A	https://www.linkedin.com/feed
CETAQUA	22/11/2023	9 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/
Aina Membrive / CETAQUA	22/11/2023	20 reactions, 0 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ainamembrive
Rcities	21/02/2023	124 Likes 15% engagement rate	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity
Rcities	23/02/2023	122 Likes 4% engagement rate	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Rcities	02/06/2023	27 Likes 2% engagement rate	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/
Rcities	11/05/2023	36 Likes 5% engagement rate	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Rcities	04/06/2023	27 Likes 2% engagement rate	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7049686660749357057
Rcities	26/06/2023	82 Likes 14% engagement rate	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7079127223793803265
Rcities	20/10/2023	81 Likes 31% engagement rate	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update
Rotterdam	14/11/23	9	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/resilient-rotterdam
Liesbeth Werleman	15/11/23	218 likes, 26 comments	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/liesbeth
Kinga Feenstra/ Rotterdam	18/11/23	71 likes, 8 comments	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kinga-feenstra_a-political

Kinga Feenstra/ Rotterdam	20/10/23	55 likes, 2 comments	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kinga
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Table 7 Individual Partners X / Twitter posts.

Twitter			
Account	Date	Engagement	Link
UP2030HE and repost by Granollers' team	14/11/23	5 reactions, 4 shares	Repost of: https://x.com/UP2030_HE/status/1724464113659638205?s=20
UP2030HE and repost by Granollers' team	22/11/23	10 reactions, 5 shares	Repost of: https://x.com/UP2030_HE/status/1727278232158814249?s=20
UP2030HE and repost by Granollers' team	22/11/23	10 reactions, 5 shares	Repost of: https://x.com/UP2030_HE/status/1727278232158814249?s=20
Icatalist and repost by Granollers' team	22/11/23	5 reactions, 2 shares	Repost of: https://x.com/icatalist/status/1727264908272869637?s=20
UP2030HE and repost by Granollers' team	02/11/23	3 reactions, 2 shares	Repost of: https://x.com/UP2030_HE/status/1720063667855655015?s=20
UP2030HE and repost by Virgínia Domingo/ Granollers	22/11/23	10 reactions, 5 shares	Repost of: https://x.com/UP2030_HE/status/1727278232158814249?s=20
Granollers	18/01/24	14 reactions, 4 shares	https://twitter.com/granollers/status/1747989634204770527
Agbar and repost by Granollers' team	23/01/24	3 reactions, 1 share	Repost of: https://twitter.com/Agbar/status/1749826823117050327
ICATALIST and repost by Granollers' team	25/01/24	4 reactions, 1 share	Repost of: https://twitter.com/icatalist/status/1750501703940546794
AGBAR clients and repost by Granollers' team	26/01/24	5 reactions, 2 shares	Repost of: https://twitter.com/AGBARclients/status/17508489293551994424

Agbar and repost by Granollers' team	29/01/24	12 reactions, 5 shares	Repost of: https://twitter.com/Agbar/status/175190817472926118 4
Irene Tsakiridou / MDAT	14/03/2024	21 impressions	https://x.com/IreneTsakiridou/status
Istanbul	14/12/2023	N/A yet	https://x.com/istanbuliklim/status
Istanbul	28/03/2024	1 like, 1 share	https://twitter.com/istanbuliklim/status
K3Y	23/03/23	Impressions: 24, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status
K3Y	12/04/23	Impressions: 70, Engagements: 2	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/
K3Y	28/04/23	Impressions: 34, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/16519071657187082 27
K3Y	26/05/23	Impressions: 80, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/16620252643127459 84
K3Y	02/06/23	Impressions: 95, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/16646386683325726 74
K3Y	07/06/2023	Impressions: 53, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/16664647673413632 05
K3Y	16/06/2023	Impressions: 54, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/16696830473089638 42
K3Y	15/11/2023	Impressions: 18, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/17248299704536599 33
K3Y	24/11/2023	Impressions: 19, Engagements: 2	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/17279910357064339 19
K3Y	12/12/2023	Impressions: 0, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/17346061908885507 25
K3Y	11/01/2024	Impressions: 5, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/17454274503249882 05
K3Y	24/01/2024	Impressions: 19, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/17501008374964883 10
K3Y	31/01/2024	Impressions: 29, Engagements: 3	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/17526769756284109 99

K3Y	08/04/2024	Impressions: 6, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/1777288754362716375
Agbar / Acquatec	08/06/2023	5 likes, 3 retweets	https://twitter.com/Agbar/status/1666772
Agbar / Acquatec	23/01/2024	3 likes, 1 retweet	https://twitter.com/Agbar/status/1749826823117050327
Agbar / Acquatec	26/01/2024	5 likes, 2 retweets	https://twitter.com/AGBARclients/status/
CIRCE	14/06/2024	2 likes, 4 retweets, 149 reproductions	https://twitter.com/fCIRCE/status/
MfC	13/12/2023	N/A	https://twitter.com/mapping4change/status
MfC	15/11/2023	0 likes, 0 retweets, 61 views	https://x.com/mapping4change/status
MfC	18/10/2023	1 like, 71 views	https://x.com/mapping4change/status?s=46
CETAQUA	22/11/2023	6 reactions, 3 shares	https://twitter.com/CETAQUA/status/
Rotterdam	20-11-23	2 likes, 1 retweet	https://x.com/ResilientRdam/status

4.3 [Newsletter & Press releases](#)

As part of the communication activities within the project, newsletters and press releases are regularly published, highlighting content relevant to the main achievements or significant events occurring during each respective period. Through the dissemination of newsletters and press releases the project ensures transparent and comprehensive communication, fostering engagement and awareness among its audience.

4.3.1 [Newsletter](#)

During the project's lifespan, twelve newsletters will be published. To date, three newsletters (December 2023, February 2024, June 2024) have been released. For the second half of the project's duration, it is planned to publish a newsletter every other month from July 2024 on until the project's completion. To streamline the graphic design and presentation of the newsletters, a campaign has been set up on Mailchimp. This facilitates consistency in branding and layout and allows for automated distribution to registered contacts. The newsletters published are included in the Annex.

Figure 11 UP2030's mailchimp campaign

Additionally, the newsletters are posted on the project website, specifically on the [communication kit page](#), where they are available for reading and downloading by all visitors. Specifically, the links are provided below:

- [UP2030 Newsletter #1](#) – December 2023
- [UP2030 Newsletter #2](#) – February 2024
- UP2030 Newsletter #3 – June 2024

Figure 12 UP2030's newsletters in website

As described in D6.1, a dedicated [registration form](#) (Figure 80) is provided on the project's website, enabling interested visitors to subscribe to UP2030's newsletters whenever updates become available. Currently, 340 people have subscribed to the UP2030's newsletter. To boost registrations for the UP2030 newsletter, corresponding posts are made on the project's social media accounts. All partners are actively involved in this effort, promoting the newsletter within their networks. This approach aims to increase visibility and attract more subscribers to stay informed about the latest developments and achievements of the project.

Figure 13 Newsletter registration form

4.3.2 [Press Release](#)

To improve the project's presence in the media, the UP2030 consortium plans to generate a minimum of four press releases. These releases will highlight milestones and interim outcomes achieved within UP2030. They will be disseminated through each partner's networks and available for access on the project website. The 1st press release has been published in M6 and reported in D6.3. The timeline for the upcoming press releases is M18 – June 2024-, M24 – December 2024 and M35 – November 2025.

4.4 [Blog Posts](#)

The UP2030 blog post page was launched in M10. On a monthly basis it is updated with the content prepared by the consortium. Below are presented the blog posts published by M16.

- Why Social Equity Matters in cities response to climate change (Fraunhofer)
- Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality (Mapping for Change)
- Belfast City joining forces with Design Clips within UP2030 project (Belfast City Council & Design Clips)
- UP2030's synergies: Achieving Climate Neutrality through Collaboration (ICLEI and Local Governments for Sustainability)
- Bringing Science into Action: Climate Resilient Urban Design in Rio de Janeiro (UCCRN)

Table 8 presents the blog post timetable and the partner responsible for preparing the content for each month from M16 (April 2024) to M36 (December 2025).

Table 8 Blog timetable

Month	Partner	Month	Partner	Month	Partner
M16	UCCRN	M23	CERTH	M30	LNEC
M17	Rcities	M24	DELTARES	M31	LIF
M18	ISOCARP	M25	LINKS	M32	VUB
M19	ICATALIST	M26	UPV	M33	ETH
M20	DREVEN	M27	ADELPHI	M34	LISBOA
M21	UIC	M28	TSPA	M35	GGGI
M22	TUD	M29	CETAQUA	M36	Fraunhofer– Coordination Team

5 Dissemination and Communication Monitoring

In D6.3 it is described that the project consortium evaluates the effectiveness of each D&C channel and activity using reporting templates. As the D&C leader, DreVen regularly requests the entire consortium to complete relevant documents every three months. This allows us to assess the overall impact of our efforts and to plan upcoming related activities effectively.

The monitoring files have been comprehensively presented in D6.3. and are summarized as follows.

- **D&C internal partner report:** This report aims to help the D&C leader of the project monitor and collect information about the relevant activities that have been carried out by the consortium partners.
- **Individual dissemination plan:** In this excel file, all partners are asked to state what types of dissemination activities they will carry out to maximize the impact of UP2030. Partners are strongly encouraged by the D&C team to carry out these activities at least once during the year, except if there is a specific reason not to and which they should communicate with the D&C leader.
- **Publications and events:** The purpose of this excel file is to facilitate the better monitoring of the dissemination of the project as regards to publications submitted and participation in various events. In addition, it aims to inform the consortium about future events relevant to the project.

These documents have been minimally modified to accommodate the needs that arose during the project implementation. Specifically, the updated version of the “D&C internal partner report” requires separating the events that partners attended in events/workshops/conferences. Moreover, this report includes a new section regarding the publications of the partners which has been removed from the excel file “publications and events”. Both documents are attached in the Annex.

5.1 Dissemination and Communication Indicators

The consortium has determined that a range of indicators is suitable for assessing the impact of D&C activities in the project. KPIs will be utilised to evaluate the project's impact. Table 9 and Table 10 outline the indicators planned for the D&C activities and performance since the start of UP2030.

Table 9 Communication activities KPIs.

Communication Activity	KPI	Status by M16
Visual Identity	Prepared in M1	Done
Project website	Online by M3 Unique visitors by M36: > 4 000	Done 5 100
Social Media	Number of posts: 1 per week Size of online community by M36: > 4 000	Ongoing 2 000

e-Newsletters and Email Campaigns	Total number of distributed e-Newsletters: 12 Total Mailing List Contact Points: > 1 500	2 newsletters distributed Total Contact points: 340
Press Releases	Total number of press releases: 4	1
Innovation Portfolio	Number of success stories: story maps for all cities	Ongoing
Communication Kit	Number of events to be distributed by the end of project > 30	Initial materials prepared and distributed in X events

Table 10 Dissemination activities KPIs.

Dissemination Activity	KPI	Status by M16
Scientific Publications	Publishing in peer-reviewed journal articles > 30 Presenting in scientific conferences > 50 At least 1 special edition led by UP2030 guest editors in a high impact journal	Total of 4 2 special editions in progress
Technical Publications	Publishing Technical Publications >20 Presenting in Technical Conferences > 20	Not performed yet
Workshops & Trainings	Workshops > 10 in 8 different countries Training tutorials > 8; webinars > 10	Total of 23 workshops
Joint Activities with Relevant Initiatives	Relevant initiatives to establish links > 15 Co-organized events > 20 Fairs to participate >20	Synergies with 3 initiatives 43 events and fairs

Source Code Repository	Number of publicly available deliverables = 24 Source code: publish to > 2 different repositories	Not performed yet
Policy Briefs	Policy recommendations and best practices > 11 (at least 1 per pilot)	Not performed yet

6 Dissemination and Communication Planned Activities

The ongoing D&C activities of UP2030 will persist in undertakings aimed at augmenting the project's impact. As the project advances even further, its updates, progress and results will be disseminated through various D&C channels, activities and tools, as elucidated in preceding sections and in D6.1 and D6.2.

The planned activities can be outlined in summary:

- Constant update of website's content.
- Enrich website content with videos from each pilot city.
- Update the UP2030 blog page on a monthly basis with engaging content. Weekly updates of social media accounts.
- Increase the number of scientific publications and proceed with technical publications.
- Publish the project's newsletter on a bimonthly basis.
- Constant monitoring of C&D actions against the target KPIs.
- Participation and organization of workshops and events.
- Establish more synergies with relevant projects and initiatives.
- Development of the Innovation Portfolio.

7 Conclusions

This document constitutes the comprehensive report of the D&C activities of UP2030 project and their impact from M7 to M16 of the project. Substantial advancements have been achieved in accordance with the outlined objectives specified in D6.1 and D6.2. Vigilant monitoring of this strategy's execution will be upheld, with progress meticulously documented in forthcoming deliverable: D6.5.

The consortium partners have demonstrated a commendable track record in effectively engaging in communication and dissemination efforts, as evidenced by their reported performance, and measured against the targeted KPIs. D&C actions will continue to undergo constant monitoring and modifications to align with the project's evolving needs, ensuring optimal visibility to stakeholders and targeted audiences.

In the dissemination of research findings, meticulous attention will continue to be devoted to maintaining accuracy, with the establishment of rigorous safeguards mechanisms for data collection and analysis.

The seamless execution of dissemination and communication actions, in accordance with the UP2030 strategy, and the collective efforts of consortium partners therein are indispensable to the project's success.

8 References

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Annex 1

The annex provides a comprehensive, date-organized overview of each workshop, conference, community event, and forum. Each entry includes the event title, date, location, event website, and details on social media dissemination (if applicable).

Table 11 Climate City Forum

Partner	Muenster
Event	Climate City Forum
Date	15/06/2023
Location	Muenster, Germany
Event website link	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/stadtforum
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	How can we work together towards the goal of climate neutrality? What can I contribute myself and where do I need support from others? Citizens, civil society, businesses, administration and politics discussed these questions at the city forum "Muenster becomes a Climate City".
Abstract/publication related to the event	N/A
Short description of the abstract/publication	N/A
Dissemination through social media	https://www.facebook.com/gutesmorgenmuenster/ A stream of the whole event and the graphic recording is under: https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/stadtforum

Source: Stadt Münster/Meike Reiners

Table 12 NetZeroCities Summer School

Partner	Muenster
Event	NetZeroCities Summer School
Date	18/07/2023 – 22/07/2023
Location	Santander, Spain
Event website link	https://netzerocities.eu/2023/08/01/netzerocities-summer-schools-helping-cities-accelerate-their-climate-transition/
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	The Summer School is designed to help cities in their climate action pathways towards climate neutrality and to support them in accelerating the design of coherent portfolios of actions and sound funding strategies. From investment planning to social innovation, cities have been sharing approaches and tools, and cooking some Climate City Contracts to move climate action forward. Beyond thematic learning, the Summer Schools are also about in-person encounters. For city representatives, they are the opportunity to openly share their progress, questions, doubts, and interests and have fruitful conversations in a safe space. These kinds of encounters are essential for Mission Cities to connect, feel empowered by each other, and get support from peers in addition to support they can get from the NetZeroCities consortium members. (Morgan, 2023)

Abstract/publication related to the event	N/A
Short description of the Abstract/publication	N/A
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Source: NetZeroCities

Table 13 NetZeroCities Summer School

Partner	Lisbon
Event	NetZeroCities Summer School
Date	19/07/2023-21/07/2023
Location	Santander, Spain
Event website link	https://netzerocities.eu/2023/08/01/netzerocities-summer-schools
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	The Summer School is designed to help cities in their climate action pathways towards climate neutrality and to support them in accelerating the design of coherent portfolios of actions and sound funding strategies. From investment planning to social innovation, cities have been sharing approaches and tools, and cooking some Climate City Contracts to move climate action forward.

Dissemination through social media	N/A
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Table 14 Los Lagos Vision Sostenible

Partner	Fraunhofer
Event	Los Lagos Vision Sostenible
Date	30/08/2023 – 31/08/2023
Location	Puerto Varas, Chile
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	Event focused on promoting entrepreneurship and the smart city industry in the Los Lagos Region, Chile 2023. The presentation focused on best practices for urban planning. The UP2030 project was introduced, together with its pilot cities and the 5UP approach.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/trinidad-fernandez

Source: Fraunhofer IAO

Table 15 Magallanes Visión Sostenible

Partner	Fraunhofer
Event	Magallanes Visión Sostenible
Date	05/09/2023 – 06/09/2023
Location	Punta Arenas, Chile
Event website link	N/A

Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	Event focused on promoting entrepreneurship and the smart city industry in the Magallanes Region, Chile 2023. The presentation focused on best practices for urban planning. The UP2030 project was introduced, together with its pilot cities and the 5UP approach.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Source: Fraunhofer IAO

Table 16 World Smart Cities Expo

Partner	Fraunhofer
Event	World Smart Cities Expo
Date	06/09/2023 – 08/09/2023
Location	Goyang, South Korea
Event website link	https://www.worldsmartcityexpo.com/fairDash.do?hl=ENG
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	World Smart City Expo 2023 is the largest smart city event in the Asia-Pacific where governments, companies, and experts from all over the world in the smart city field come together to create a city of the future. The presentation focused on presenting new urban approaches to climate action, the UP2030 project was introduced to the audience as well as its transformational objectives through the 5UP approach.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/catalina-diaz

Source: Fraunhofer IAO

Table 17 Benicàssim Conference

Partner	UPV
Event	Benicàssim Conference
Date	20/09/2023- 21/09/2023
Location	Benicàssim, Castellón, Spain
Event website link	https://baio.webs.upv.es/
Role in the event	Co- organizer
Short description of the event	To promote applied research and transfer in the aforementioned areas, this workshop enabled direct interaction between a select group of experts from different universities and companies in the sector. The workshop explored avenues for effective collaboration in research and development (R&D) projects and best practices in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and mathematics education. The workshop was also an excellent opportunity to present some of the research and transfer projects that we are currently developing in university-industry collaborations to society.
Abstract/publication related to the event	N/A
Short description of the Abstract/publication	N/A

Dissemination through social media	N/A
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Table 18 "Urban Environments and Human Health in Lisbon" Conference

Partner	LNEC
Event	"Urban Environments and Human Health in Lisbon" Conference
Date	26/09/2023
Location	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC), Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	Instituto de Saúde Ambiental (ulisboa.pt)
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	This conference presented ideas, ongoing initiatives in the city of Lisbon and results of studies that relate environmental determinants (temperature, air pollution, waste, exposure to greenery, etc.) and human health, carried out in partnership between Lisbon, LISBOA, ISAMB, and the LNEC itself. The event counts 167 participants.
Dissemination through social media	N/A
Source: CML	

Table 19 "Urban Environments and Human Health in Lisbon" Conference

Partner	Lisbon
Event	"Urban Environments and Human Health in Lisbon" Conference
Date	26/09/2023
Location	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC), Lisbon, Portugal

Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Co- organizer
Short description of the event	This conference presented ideas, ongoing initiatives in the city of Lisbon and results of studies that relate environmental determinants (temperature, air pollution, waste, exposure to greenery, etc.) and human health, carried out in partnership between Lisbon, LISBOA, ISAMB, and LNEC.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

(Source: Lisbon)

Table 20 ARSINOE Exploitation Workshop: Paving the Path to Climate Resilience

Partner	Lisbon
Event	ARSINOE Exploitation Workshop: Paving the Path to Climate Resilience
Date	28/09/2023
Location	Barcelona, Spain
Event website link	www.arsinoe-project.eu
Role in the event	Participant

Short description of the event	ARSINOE Exploitation Workshop are collaborative events where participants from city representatives, academia, community organizations, the European Commission to the United Nations, came together to define pathways for a resilient transformation across Europe and the globe.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 21 Visit/work Meeting with the Viena Municipality

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Visit/work Meeting with the Viena Municipality
Date	28/09/2023
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	The Lisbon Municipality presented some of the current projects related to the good solutions adopted in Lisbon towards climate neutrality , including the UP2030 project.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 22 Adaptation Futures 2023

Partner	UCCRN
Event	Adaptation Futures 2023
Date	02/10/2023 - 06/10/2023
Location	HYBRID FORMAT (Montréal, Canada) Conference Secretariat – JPdL International
Event website link	https://adaptationfutures.com/
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	<p>The Adaptation Futures Conference series is the premier international conference devoted entirely to climate change adaptation, bringing together researchers, policymakers, practitioners, industry representatives and communicators to present their work on adaptation, discuss emerging and cutting-edge issues, learn what others are doing, and build networks.</p> <p>UCCRN edu presented a panel session within the Adaptation Futures Conference that aims at confronting the educational</p>

	<p>approaches, methods and tools being developed by the UCCRN_edu community. UCCRN panelists and other invited speakers discussed with participants how to enhance multi-disciplinary education, delivering climate-resilient design, planning and governance of cities theoretical, and practical skills.</p>
<p>Abstract/publication related to the event</p>	<p>UCCRN edu Shaping and sharing tools and methods for bridging the gaps between science and climate-resilient urban design and planning.</p>
<p>Short description of the abstract/publication</p>	<p>UCCRN edupresented a panel session within the Adaptation Futures Conference that aims at confronting the educational approaches, methods and tools being developed by the UCCRN_edu community. UCCRN panelists and other invited speakers discussed with participants how to enhance multi-disciplinary education, delivering climate-resilient design, planning and governance of cities theoretical, and practical skills.</p>
<p>Dissemination through social media</p>	<p>https://www.instagram.com/p/Cx5PTz4liC5 https://www.instagram.com/p/CyBoDq4sc3-/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/theo-uccrn-education-460440236</p>

Source: UCCRN

Table 23 Urban Mobility Days

Partner	Fraunhofer
Event	Urban Mobility Days
Date	04/10/2023 – 06/10/2023
Location	Seville, Spain
Event website link	Urban Mobility Days 2023 - European Commission (europa.eu)
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	Urban Mobility Days was an event where politicians, local authorities, industry, and urban transport practitioners met with the European Commission. The objective of the event was to connect, share and discuss the path forward for a sustainable, innovative, and equitable future for Europe’s urban mobility. With a stand at the marketplace, the UP2030 project objectives and activities were promoted.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity

Source: Fraunhofer IAO

Table 24 European Green Capital & European Green Leaf Ceremony 2025

Partner	Lisbon
Event	European Green Capital & European Green Leaf Ceremony 2025
Date	05/10/2023
Location	Tallinn, Estonia
Event website link	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/european-green-capital-european-green-leaf-ceremony
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	"Lisbon's contribution to the European Challenge for climate neutrality by 2030" at the European Green Capital & European Green Leaf Ceremony 2025. These two awards are promoting and recognizing the environmental achievements and initiatives of European cities that are strongly committed to making sustainability one of their top priorities. The program extends to acknowledge the European Green Capital Network, composed of all winning and finalist cities since the launch of the competition, back in 2010. This ceremony recognizes the efforts made by European cities to reach the European Green Deal goals and it is also an occasion to gather and enjoy this moment together, sharing good practices and always bringing new ideas to the table for the future.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 25 Smart Cities Summit 2023

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Smart Cities Summit 2023
Date	12/10/2023
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	https://portugalsmartcities.fil.pt/
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	The "Smart Cities" Concept covers more than mobility, digital platforms or sustainability. The fundamental objective of a Smart City is the incorporation of all these areas to improve the lives of citizens around the world. Portugal Smart Cities Summit is the place of convergence and the physical marketplace for creating opportunities for the national and international markets. The

	Lisbon Municipality presented some of the current projects related to the scope of the Summit, including the UP2030 project.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 26 European Week of Regions and Cities

Partner	Lisbon
Event	European Week of Regions and Cities
Date	12/10/2023
Location	Brussels, Belgium
Event website link	Achieving Climate Neutral Cities through the Regeneration of Historic Urban Areas European Week of Regions and Cities (europa.eu)
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	The session discussed how to regenerate Historic urban areas in the co-creation of Climate Neutral City Contracts (CCC) for the EU Mission on Cities. A fresh new Policy Report issued by H2020 Innovation Actions CENTRINNO, T-Factor and HUB-IN was introduced; policymakers, city makers and researchers with selected Mission Cities discussed 3 main operational challenges in CCC (creative spaces; temporary uses; heritage revitalization) in thematic world-café and peer-learning exercise.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 27 Workshop UP2030 Adaptive Pathways

Partner	MDAT
Event	Workshop UP2030 Adaptive Pathways
Date	17/10/2023
Location	Thessaloniki, Greece
Event website link	https://mdat.gr/2024/04/08/
Role in the event	Co- organizer together with the Municipality of Thessaloniki
Short description of the event	<p>The workshop hosted more than 30 key actors from the area, including citizens, municipal employees, elected councilors of the area.</p> <p>The workshop aimed at drafting with the participants the roadmap to reaching the vision of the UP2030 project for the pilot area</p>

under the pillars of climate neutrality, just transition and resilience. More specifically the scope was to pave the way for practical, adaptive strategies aligned with the local pilot objectives and vision.

The participants proposed specific actions, voted on the most significant ones and analyzed further how each action can be successfully implemented.

Dissemination through social media <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/STtMBeZGzLggKfCG/>

(Source: MDAT)

Event 2

Table 28 UP2030 Spatial Assessment Workshop Thessaloniki

Partner	MDAT
Event	UP2030 Spatial Assessment Workshop Thessaloniki
Date	17/10/2023
Location	Thessaloniki, Greece
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Co- organizer together with the Municipality of Thessaloniki
Short description of the event	<p>The participants were elderly people living in the area.</p> <p>The scopes of the workshop were to engage residents in an assessment process of the neighborhood characteristics and their impact on the well-being and health of the residents, as well as to understand the interrelations between the sustainable urban development of the area and climate neutrality, resilience and just transition.</p> <p>The organizers presented the UP2030 project, the scope of the workshop, the need to take urgent actions to reduce emissions and make our cities resilient to climate change improving the life quality of the citizens.</p> <p>The participants were divided in small groups and using the printed maps of the area, colorful pencils and stickers they spotted their daily routes and the specific needs/barriers of the area, what needs to be changed and the current challenges.</p>
Dissemination through social media	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/E32JYr7kjuzckuS/

Source: Irene Tsakiridou

Table 29 Life Lungs 2nd Technical Meeting - The role of cities in combating climate change"

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Life Lungs 2nd Technical Meeting - The role of cities in combating climate change"
Date	18/10/2023
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	An oral presentation was made by the Lisbon Municipality, entitled: "Lisbon strategy to climate neutrality by 2030", which included the presentation of the UP2030 project.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 30 Ciutats Enfront L'emergència Climàtica: Claus per una Transició Justa

Partner	Granollers
Event	Cities Facing Climate Emergency. Keys to a Fair Transition.
Date	18/10/2023
Location	Barcelona, Spain

Event website link	https://www.institutmetropoli.cat/ca/noticias/ciutats-enfront-emergencia-climatica-jornada/
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	There were presented some tools to help cities and governments and managers to deal with climate change in their cities. Also has been identified which of them really promote a just transition that reduces socio-economic and territorial inequalities.
Abstract/publication related to the event	<p>The conclusions of the event was collected in a publication that contents the main research on the possible opportunities and social and environmental injustices that climate transition can bring for urban areas, to encourage just truly transformative transitions. The publication gives valuable reflections around:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Urban adaptation and mitigation to achieve a just transition - New narratives and transformative alliances in the face of the climate emergency
Short description of the abstract/publication	Theoretical reflections and case studies located in urban contexts deal with various elements that influence the climate just transition. In addition to addressing the most recognized axes of inequality, such as income, age, or place of residence, it also incorporates new perspectives that emerge from feminist research and the framework of intersectionality and that allow to broaden the focus towards LGTBQ+ people, racialized people, gender gaps or situations of water and energy poverty.
<p>Source: © 2024 INSTITUT METROPOLI</p>	
Dissemination through social media	N.65 – CITIES FACING THE CLIMATE EMERGENCY: KEYS TO A FAIR TRANSITION

Table 31 EURESFO

Partner	LNEC
Event	EURESFO
Date	18/10/2023-20/10/2023
Location	Cascais, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	10 th edition of the European Urban Resilience Forum (EURESFO) in ICLEI member Cascais, Portugal. Participation of LNEC staff.
Dissemination through social media	ICLEI Europe •• News (iclei-europe.org)

Table 32 EURESFO: “Designing Resilient, Climate-Neutral Cities: District-focused Innovations”

Partner	Rcities
Event	EURESFO: “Designing Resilient, Climate-Neutral Cities: District-focused Innovations”
Date	18/10/2023-20/10/2023
Location	Cascais, Portugal
Event website link	https://urbanresilienceforum.eu/
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	European cities are leading in climate goals, aiming for climate-neutrality as part of the European Commission's mission. They're starting with district-level strategies to expand climate initiatives, combining local and city policies for a human-focused sustainable transition. During this event, Rotterdam and Milan presented the UP2030 pilots.
Abstract/publication related to the event	<p>Resilience-makers, resilience innovators, resilience providers, and resilience supporters gathered in Cascais for the 2023 EURESFO</p> <p>Over 350 participants of 44 countries, from city representatives, academia, community organizations, the European Commission to the United Nations, came together at the 2023 edition of the European Urban Resilience Forum in Cascais, Portugal to define pathways for a resilient transformation across Europe and the globe.</p> <p>Reflecting on progress made in the field of urban resilience over the past decade, when opening the forum, Virginijus Sinkevičius, European Commissioner for the Environment, Oceans and Fisheries highlighted: “Resilience is a word that we hear more and</p>

more – the response that we need to a decade of crises... We never know what’s around the corner. But, with an integrated approach, we are better prepared.”

The three-day event featured 40+ sessions and workshops with over 100 speakers and moderators. They reflected on a changed climate and new extreme events that have become ever-present. The forum discussed innovative governance models and funding schemes to deal with multi-hazard scenarios, more frequent climate extremes, and overlapping crises, diving deep into multi-level structures and opportunities for managing and funding adaptation projects and action.

Dissemination through social media

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity>

Source: Rcities

Table 33 EURESFO: “Designing Resilient, Climate-Neutral Cities: District-focused Innovations”

Partner	Rotterdam
Event	EURESFO: “Designing Resilient, Climate-Neutral Cities: District-focused Innovations”
Date	18/10/2023-20/10/2023
Location	Cascais, Portugal
Event website link	https://urbanresilienceforum.eu/
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	Kinga Feenstra, project manager of Rotterdam UP2030 was a speaker at the panel on “Designing Resilient, Climate-Neutral Cities: District-focused Innovations”.

Abstract/publication related to the event	N/A
Short description of the abstract/publication	N/A
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Source: Trinidad Fernandez (Fraunhofer)

Table 34 Visit/work Meeting with the Lathi Municipality

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Visit/work Meeting with the Lathi Municipality
Date	20/10/2023
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	The Lisbon Municipality presented to the Lathi Municipality some of the current projects which are currently being developed, including the UP2030 project.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 35 Climate City Week

Partner	Muenster
Event	Climate City Week
Date	21/10/2023 -27/10/2023
Location	Muenster, Germany
Event website link	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/rueckblick-klimastadt-woche
Short description of the event	Together with 20 partners, 30 tours and discussion events were offered at 20 different locations in Muenster as part of the Climate City Week from October 21 st -27 th , 2023. Whether on foot, by bike, on the double-decker electric bus, at the weekend, in the evening, or digitally, in the lab or the pub- there was plenty to discover.
Abstract/publication related to the event	A review with lots of facts, photos and videos can be found on the website https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/startseite/klimastadt-woche
Short description of the Abstract/publication	N/A
<p>Source: Stadt Münster/ Michael C. Moeller</p>	
Dissemination through social media	https://www.instagram.com/unserklima2030/?hl=de

Table 36 Major Cities of Europe Annual Conference 2023

Partner	MAG
Event	Major Cities of Europe Annual Conference 2023
Date	25/10/2023 -27/10/2023
Location	Prato, Italy
Event website link	https://majorcities.eu/conferences/2023-prato/
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	<p>Major cities of Europe’s mission are to support local governments in sharing experiences, solutions and strategies in the use of information and communication technologies and leading-edge innovation in the administration of local governments and in the development of new services for the well-being and the wealth of their constituents and for the local economy.</p> <p>UP2030 was presented by Samuele Baroni from MAG during the plenary session and included in the most innovative projects of Maggioli Group Research and Development department regarding smart cities.</p>
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/major-cities-of-europe_majorcitiesofeurope-mceprato2023-conferencemoments-activity

Source: MAG

Table 37 Benchmarking Workshop

Partner	BH
Event	Benchmarking Workshop
Date	26/10/2023- 27/10/2023
Location	Barcelona, Spain
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	<p>In a two day in-person Workshop organized by the Universitat Internacional de Catalunya (UIC) in Barcelona, Buro Happold together with other partners mainly from the Benchmarking Taskforce (WP2, T2.2, incl. TU Delft, TSPA in person as well as more online participants) developed methods to integrate a holistic form of benchmarking into the development of the Cities’ visions and later adaptive pathways.</p> <p>The workshop was held in a hybrid form with partly in-person and partly online sessions that enabled all participants to give input. The format was shaped by inputs from different participants, including input from Buro Happold with regards to insights in the fields of Climate Change mitigation and adaptation, as well as interactive discussions and content development of a benchmarking scheme to be applied in the later process within the partner Cities.</p> <p>In line with the three core pillars of the UP2030 project, the topics Carbon Neutral, Resilient and Just Cities were represented within the developed benchmarking scheme. Further, the workshop aimed at and succeeded in linking the benchmarking characteristics to the KPIs.</p> <p>In addition to the content development by the participants from the UP consortium, the workshop also offered possibilities for participation of master students from UIC.</p>
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/activity

Table 38 Global Green Growth Week

Partner	GGGI
Event	Global Green Growth Week
Date	27/10/2023
Location	Seoul, South Korea & online via Zoom

Event website link	https://globalgreengrowthweek.gggi.org/
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	The Global Green Growth Week was hosted by the GGGI that served as knowledge-sharing process of scalable solutions that address the ongoing climate crises. Up to 40 sessions were held during this week, covering four major themes of GGGI’s green growth index, including natural capital, green economic opportunity, efficient and sustainable resource use, and social inclusion. The session organized by GGGI’s Hungary office which was held on the last day of the week-long conference, titled “Research Policy Interface to Upscale Multi-Level Climate Action” aimed to explore the importance of a collaborative and informed approach to climate change by introducing projects that can be replicated and upscaled. The UP2030 project was presented during this session.
Abstract/publication related to the event	N/A
Short description of the Abstract/publication	N/A
Dissemination through social media	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cHpX8LUIbaE&t=1692s (Recording of Session) https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7119681727026884608 and https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122515897981808641

Table 39 KlimaBarCamp (part of the Climate Week)

Partner	Muenster
Event	KlimaBarCamp (part of the Climate Week)
Date	27/10/2023
Location	Muenster, Germany
Event website link	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/rueckblick-klimastadt-woche
Short description of the event	The KlimaBarCamp on October 27 th marked the end of Climate City Week and offered the opportunity to pick up on impulses, ideas and projects from the week, as well as the chance to introduce completely new aspects relating to the topic of climate. In the spirit

	of a BarCamp, people exchanged ideas, inspired each other, critically questioned each other and took away a lot of inspiration - whether as food for thought, concrete projects or ideas.
Abstract/publication related to the event	A summary including photo documentation of all the results and a video with sound bites from some of the participants is here: https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/dokumentation-klimabarcamp
Short description of the abstract/publication	Photo documentation and video
Source: Stadt Muenster/Julian Meyer	
Dissemination through social media	https://www.facebook.com/stadt.muenster https://www.facebook.com/gutesmorgenmuenster

Table 40 Alcoy Artificial Intelligence & Optimization workshop

Partner	UPV
Event	Alcoy Artificial Intelligence & Optimization workshop
Date	07/11/ 2023 - 08/11/2023
Location	Alcoy, Spain
Event website link	https://alcoytech.webs.upv.es/
Role in the event	Co- organizer

Short description of the event	The Alcoy Artificial Intelligence & Optimization workshop, organized in collaboration with the UPV, aimed to promote the efficient and sustainable digitization of various sectors, including business, industry, education, and society. It served as a platform for experts from both academia and industry to engage in applied research and knowledge transfer, fostering collaboration in research and development and showcasing projects that result from academia-industry partnerships.
Abstract/publication related to the event	N/A
Short description of the Abstract/publication	N/A
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 41 Visit/work Meeting with District 6 of the Bucharest Municipality

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Visit/work Meeting with District 6 of the Bucharest Municipality
Date	09/11/2023
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	Project title: Strategic Planning in the fields of Digital Transformation and Green Energy – SMART 6 Beneficiary: Bucharest District 6. The Lisbon Municipality presented to the Bucharest District 6 some of the current projects which are currently being developed, including the UP2030 project
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 42 UP2030 General Assembly

Partner	LNEC
Event	UP2030 General Assembly
Date	13/11/2023 -15/11/2023
Location	LNEC, Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A

Role in the event	Co-organizer
Short description of the event	The UP2030 three-day general assembly at LNEC hosted 67 participants, with local organization managed by the LNEC and CML teams. The first day was dedicated to taking the participants on a technical visit to explore the Alvalade, Lisbon, pilot borough. This dissemination initiative was the responsibility of CML, LNEC and LEN.
<p data-bbox="613 1360 1008 1388">Source: Maria do Céu Almeida/LNEC</p>	
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 43 UP2030 General Assembly

Partner	Budapest
Event	UP2030 General Assembly
Date	13/11/2023-15/11/2023
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A

Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	The UP2030 project had its 1st General Assembly held from 13th to 15th November in Lisbon. This assembly united city representatives, research institutions, and solution providers forming the project consortium, and offering a forum for in-depth discussions and strategic planning within UP2030. Throughout the assembly, partners assumed the spotlight, presenting their progress in implementation, outcomes and highlighting challenges encountered across project phases. Through collaborative discussions significant strides were showcased, depicting achievements, and outlining the projected forthcoming actions.
Abstract/publication related to the event	N/A
Short description of the Abstract/publication	N/A
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 44 Course on Integrating Water in Urban Planning | Nature-based Solutions

Partner	LNEC
Event	Course on Integrating Water in Urban Planning Nature-based Solutions
Date	20/11/2023 -23/11/2023
Location	LNEC, Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	Capacity building training event (14 hours) for municipality staff from different departments (including public space management, sanitation, urbanization, and green spaces, energy, and climate adaptation) of Lisbon, with a total of 25 participants.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Source: Maria do Céu Almeida/LNEC

Table 45 Tools for the Greenhouse Gas-neutral Municipality: Climate Fund

Partner	Muenster
Event	Tools for the Greenhouse Gas-neutral Municipality: Climate Fund
Date	21/11/2023
Location	Virtual Event
Event website link	www.klimaschutz.de/agentur
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	Information event on the establishment of a municipal climate fund to support third-party projects.
Abstract/publication related to the event	Tools for the greenhouse gas-neutral municipality: climate fund
Short description of the Abstract/publication	Summary of a possible procedure in pdf format and web links to the theme climate fund.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 46 Final Meeting and Conference of Climatubers (Erasmus+ Project)

Partner	Granollers
Event	Final Meeting and Conference of Climatubers (Erasmus+ Project)
Date	22/11/2023
Location	Barcelona, Spain
Event website link	https://epale.ec.europa.eu/en/content/climatubers-final-conference
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	It presented innovative approach methodologies for Climate education and climate action through participatory video.
Abstract/publication related to the event	Document of political recommendations of the project at European level Climatubers has drawn up a document of political recommendations based on the experience and evaluation of the 5 participating countries (France, Estonia, Austria, Italy and Spain), as well as the dialogues held with key agents in European scale and the existing literature. This document recognizes three main challenges that link the climate crisis, digital skills, social inclusion and climate action. Participatory video is proposed as a methodology that allows the implementation of programs and policies aimed at these challenges, at the local and European level. The aim of the document is to promote the use of participatory video in relation to a holistic perspective of the climate crisis, which promotes social inclusion and improves people's digital skills. Six recommendations are collected, and it is mainly aimed at: -Political and technical decision-makers, at national and regional level. -Local authorities, councils and public workers. -NGOs, educational institutions and organized civil society. The document has been prepared in English and can be consulted on this page in the attached documents: https://www.granollers.cat/sites/default/files/pagina/2024/01/o5.3_policy_paper.pdf
Short description of the abstract/publication	The project Climatubers, funded by the EU under the Erasmus+ program, has organized a conference about innovative methodologies for education and climate action through Participatory Video. The conference took place on November 22 th at Espai Jove Fontana, Barcelona, with up to 25 attendees in person and 16 online attendees. Among the attendees counted environmental and social workers from local administrations, participatory video practitioners, representatives of NGOs and other associations, and teachers. The objective of the Climatubers project is tackling climate change and social inclusion through the participatory video (PV) method. PV facilitates improving digital skills while sharing personal climate change experiences. With PV, the devastating effects of the climate crisis can be rendered visible, empowering vulnerable communities to raise their voice and advocate for social change. The project, funded by the Erasmus+ programme, has been tested in five pilot cases throughout Europe, specifically in Austria, France, Spain, Italy, and Estonia. After

	<p>three years of work, the project has produced 19 videos, training modules freely available online, a comprehensive evaluation report, and the policy recommendations provided in this document. Climatubers’ framework and the resulting policy recommendations are aligned with specific EU initiatives and policy instruments like the Social Climate Fund under the European Green Deal, the Paris Agreement, or the Sustainable Development Goals. The project has also considered the Education for Climate Initiative or The Pillar of Social Rights, as well as the National Adaptation Plans at the national level. The policy recommendations have been developed based on a comprehensive mixed-method evaluation assessment, policy dialogue sessions with key actors in the field of climate change, and existing literature.</p>
Dissemination through social media	<p>https://climatubers.org/climatubers-news-5-climatubers-online-course-and-eu-video-map/ https://x.com/climatubers/status/1727249313523204120</p>

Table 47 Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design

Partner	Budapest
Event	Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design
Date	30/11/2023
Location	Delft, Netherlands & online
Event website link	https://just-city.org/conferences/practice/#
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	The Symposium “Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design” (30 th NOV at TUD, 1 and 5 th DEC 2023 online) aims to foster discussions and exchange that allow us to take a step further in the formulation of frameworks, indicators and benchmarks for the practical application of the concept.
Abstract/publication related to the event	Healthy Streets [®] methodology in Budapest
Short description of the abstract/publication	A one-page abstract was submitted for this symposium, and a presentation was prepared for the cities' panel/track on the 30 th of November 2023. Budapest’s presentation was concerned with the city’s adaptation of the Healthy Streets [®] initiative in Budapest and the related call for application for funding for municipalities.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 48 Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design

Partner	Rotterdam
Event	Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design
Date	30/11/2023
Location	Delft, Netherlands & online
Event website link	https://just-city.org/conferences/practice/%23:~
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	The Symposium “Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design” (30 th November at TUD, 1 st and 5 th December 2023 online) aimed to foster discussions and exchange that allow us to take a step further in the formulation of frameworks, indicators and benchmarks for the practical application of the concept
Abstract/publication related to the event	A policy analysis of Resilient BoTu 2028: Principles and Transferability
Short description of the Abstract/publication	A one-page abstract was submitted for this symposium, and a presentation was prepared for the cities’ panel/track on the 30 th of November. Rotterdam’s presentation was concerned with the city’s current efforts under UP2030, e.g. the co-creation process of the framework that will be based on the "Resilient BoTu 2028" approach.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 49 Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design

Partner	Rcities
Event	Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design
Date	30/11/2023
Location	Delft, Netherlands & online
Event website link	https://www.spatialplanningtudelft.org/news/symposium-benchmarking-spatial-justice/#:~:text=On%2030%20November%202023%20we,in%20policymaking%2C%20planning%20and%20design
Role in the event	Participant

<p>Short description of the event</p>	<p>TUD hosted a three-day symposium on benchmarking spatial justice on the 30th of November 2023. The event aimed to foster discussions and exchange of knowledge regarding the measurement and evaluation of spatial justice in policymaking, planning and design. The symposium was held at the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment of the Delft University of Technology, and it was organized by the TUD's Centre for the Just City, in collaboration with the Horizon Europe UP2030 project and the Delft Design for Values Institute.</p>
<p>Abstract/publication related to the event</p>	<p>On day one the plenary session included a city-panel to present the UP2030 project and its approach, with contributions from the pilot cities of Budapest and Rotterdam. RCities presented the BoTu pilot on behalf of the Rotterdam Resilient BoTu team (Rotterdam is a member city of network of Resilient Cities and RCities is liaison partner of Rotterdam in UP2030):</p> <p>Resilient BoTu 2028 is an integrated program with the goal of making Bospolder and Tussendijken the first resilient district in Rotterdam. The way towards the establishment of this program was paved by many different policy pathways and needs, combined with district-specific issues, and city-wide transitions. At the core, the philosophy and structure of this program seek to facilitate long-term sustainable development of making BoTu Rotterdam's first resilient district. To enable this sustainable change, the focus is laid on social and community resilience at the heart of this program, as well as leveraging urban transitions, such as the energy transition and climate adaptation, to strengthen social resilience.</p>
<p>Dissemination through social media</p>	<p>N/A</p>

Table 50 Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design

Partner	UCCRN
Event	Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design
Date	05/12/2023
Location	Delft, Netherlands & online
Event website link	https://just-city.org/conferences/practice/
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	The Symposium 'Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design aims to foster discussions and exchanges that allow to take a step further in the formulation of frameworks, indicators and benchmarks for the practical application of the concept.
Abstract/publication related to the event	Fostering Spatial Justice through Climate-Resilient Design and Planning: Key findings of UCCRN Third Report on Climate and Cities (ARC3.3) and lessons from the Urban Design Climate Workshops
Short description of the Abstract/publication	A section of the Planning, Architecture and Design Element of the Third Assessment Report on Climate Change and Cities (ARC3.3) 2022-2024 developed by UCCRN is dedicated to assessing how to embed environmental and climate justice in architecture, urban design and city planning. This section identifies emerging definitions and practices in pursuit of climate justice in urban development processes and possible pathways for just climate-

	resilient design dealing with elements of recognition, rights, responsibilities, distribution and procedures. The work here presented aims to bring together key findings of the ARC 3.3 assessment and the practice-based lessons gained through the implementation of the UCCRN Urban Climate Design Workshops, developed by UCCRN experts since 2015.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 51 Workshop Citizen Voices in Biodiversity (Workshop Dies Natalis)

Partner	TUD
Event	Workshop Citizen Voices in Biodiversity (Workshop Dies Natalis)
Date	08/01/2024 - 12/01/2024
Location	Rotterdam, Netherlands
Event website link	https://www.tudelft.nl/en/2023/bk/join-the-dies-delta-week-from-8-12-january
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	As the climate crisis deepens, the importance of biodiversity is increasingly recognized. Large municipalities such as Rotterdam and The Hague have already implemented monitoring plans and measures to strengthen biodiversity. Citizen Voices in Biodiversity (BIO-CiVo) is a Resilient Delta Kick-starter project developing a digital platform to engage citizens in thinking about biodiversity. In this workshop, the project team and participants will explore and test the current design of the platform. The BIO-CiVo workshop is open to anyone with an interest in biodiversity, and participation about deltas.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 52 1st Visioning Workshop Budapest

Partner	Budapest
Event	1 st Visioning Workshop Budapest
Date	17/01/2024
Location	Budapest, Hungary
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	N/A
Short description of the event	The workshop began with a brief overview of UP2030, where the project's framework and desired outcomes were presented. Following this, participants were divided into three groups, each

	<p>assigned to one of the specific themes of resilience, just transition, or carbon neutrality.</p> <p>Participants in each group were encouraged to share their observations related to the assigned theme, generating a wealth of ideas and suggestions that could form the basis of the city's vision when further elaborated.</p> <p>In the next stage of the workshop, the previously formulated goals, such as engaging market players, exploring methods of societal engagement, and fostering dialogue with the local community, will be reviewed. Short, medium, and long-term steps necessary for achieving these goals, as well as obstacles were identified. It was noted that not all objectives of the UP2030 project align with the interests of the local community. For example, while the methodology of Healthy Streets[®] may promote reducing parking spaces, there may be resistance from the local community.</p> <p>Finally, the next steps were determined, focusing on strengthening collaboration and continuing the urban visioning process.</p>
Abstract/publication related to the event	A presentation was prepared on the results under the title "1st Workshop Knowledge Sharing Budapest".
Short description of the abstract/publication	A presentation was prepared about the results, which was delivered at the online event titled "2024 UP2030 Cities & Liaisons bi-monthly meeting" to our project partners.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 53 Workshop #2: Vision on “Neutral neighbourhoods in Granollers, habitable and desirable”

Partner	Granollers
Event	Workshop #2: Vision on “Neutral neighbourhoods in Granollers, habitable and desirable”
Date	24/01/2024
Location	Granollers, Spain
Event website link	https://www.granollers.cat/ajuntament/up2030
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	<p>The purposes of the 2nd workshop in Granollers and the meeting with internal and external stakeholders were:</p> <p>Brief introduction of La Bòbila objectives within UP2030, validation needs and barriers results from the 1st Workshop by problem tree, presentation of ongoing urban planning projects of Granollers, around sector 129, in the short and midterm, so that stakeholders</p>

	<p>have relevant information about what will happen around sector 129, and that this starting point serves them to visualize the future neighborhood by Montserrat Òdena. This presentation followed the co-creation of a common vision and strategy for the future neighborhood of La Bòbila. Finally, a talk on transformative strategies in cities to face climate emergency and diversity, by Hug March, and the next steps. There were 38 participants.</p>
Dissemination through social media	<p>https://www.granollers.cat/agenda/medi-ambient/2n-taller https://participa311-granollers.diba.cat/processes/up2030</p>

Source: © 2024 Ajuntament de Granollers

Table 54 Blood, Sweat & Tears: Learnings from Citizen Voice, a bottom-up open research project (Teaming Up Across Domains)

Partner	TUD
Event	Blood, Sweat & Tears: Learnings from Citizen Voice, a bottom-up open research project (Teaming Up Across Domains)
Date	27/01/ 2024
Location	Utrecht, Netherlands
Event website link	https://tdcc.nl/evenementen/teaming-up-across-domains/
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	Teaming up with the project was the Research Data Alliance NL (RDA-NL), the Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG), and Local Digital Currency Communities(DCCs), in conversations and hands-on sessions on how progress through collaboration can be accomplished.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 55 Empowering Citizen Participation in Climate Action with Digital Platforms

Partner	TUD
Event	Empowering Citizen Participation in Climate Action with Digital Platforms
Date	27/01/2024
Location	Delft, Netherlands
Event website link	https://www.tudelft.nl/evenementen/2024/open-science/empowering-citizen-participation-in-climate-action-with-digital-platforms
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	<p>Cities are responding to climate risks by setting ambitious sustainability targets, depending on citizen support for various urban interventions. With approximately 60% of the built environment privately owned in Dutch cities, citizen engagement is crucial for the success of climate initiatives. In recent years, citizen engagement in urban planning has incorporated digital platforms tapping into their potential to enable remote participation and enhance governance transparency, among other benefits.</p> <p>However, many existing digital platforms for citizen engagement in climate action remain underutilised. The BIO-CiVo and the Citizens meet Climate (CmC) studies adopt a user-centric perspective to analyse the interface design of over ten digital platforms and identify design elements that hinder or foster engagement. The analysis highlights three main interface issues: complex navigation, information overload, and limited opportunities for action.</p> <p>To overcome these limitations, two prototypes has been developed with a user-centered interface to empower citizens with clear information and actionable steps. The prototypes were tested in workshop settings with positive feedback from participants, corroborating the importance of user-centric interface design in ensuring effective citizen engagement. In this lecture, an analysis and platforms were presented and there was an opportunity to experiment with the prototypes.</p>
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 56 Mission Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt)

Partner	Granollers
Event	Mission Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt)
Date	06/02/2024 and 29/02/2024
Location	Virtual Event

Event website link	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/the-mission/about-mip4adapt https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85367623797?pwd=dFM3MXhDemFla2QwZUN1Y1dIYjR5QT09
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	<p>MIP4Adapt is carrying out a training program on citizen and stakeholder participation. This program consists of eight sessions (with two dates each) and is designed for the regions adhering to the Adaptation Mission. The goal is to guide them through the essential aspects and proven methods for effective participation in climate adaptation.</p> <p>The Granollers’ team made a presentation (two sessions) followed by questions and answers addressed from the participants: The focus of the presentation done by Granollers was “Designing an engagement strategy, based on experience in participatory work in Granollers”. Granollers’ team was invited by Icatalist.</p>
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 57 Workshop #2 Visioning #Rethink Carbon Neutrality and Climate Resilience

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Vision Workshop #Rethink Carbon Neutrality and Climate Resilience
Date	28/02/2024
Location	Palácio Galveias, Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	N/A
Short description of the event	N/A
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Source: CML-DMCom

Table 58 UP2030 StepUPLxALL

Partner	LNEC
Event	UP2030 StepUPLxALL
Date	28/02/2024
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Co-organizer and speaker
Short description of the event	This event, centered on the vision for neutrality, aimed to highlight the importance of cities in responding to the current challenges of climate resilience, with an approach to “net-zero neighborhoods” applied to Lisbon, with the parish of Alvalade as the pilot area. The

	aim is to continue the work carried out in this parish, with the various local actors and partners to face the challenge of this transition until 2030, through the promotion and implementation of local solutions.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Source: Anna Sofia Serra, CML

Table 59 Muenster Climate City Contract Event

Partner	Muenster
Event	Muenster Climate City Contract Event
Date	28/02/24
Location	Muenster, Germany
Event website link	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/klimastadtvertrag
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	On February 28 th , 130 representatives from across the city gathered in the historic town hall to sign their contributions to the first version of Münster's Climate City Agreement. The participants signed yellow plaques – each plaque a contribution – and hung them on a display wall, creating an impressive overall picture at the end.
Abstract/publication related to the event	Climate City Contract (CCC): https://www.stadt-muenster.de/fileadmin/user_upload/stadt-muenster/klimastadt/pdf/20240325_CCC_Muenster_Commitment_final.pdf Contributions of urban society: https://www.stadt-muenster.de/fileadmin/user_upload/stadt-muenster/klimastadt/pdf/Klimastadt-Vertrag_Beitraege_der_Stadtgesellschaft_final.pdf
Short description of the Abstract/publication	The CCC, which the EU requires as a part of the application for the "Mission Label", describes how the path to becoming a climate neutral city is being strategically pursued. Making Muenster a Climate City requires contributions from the entire urban community. All contributions received between the launch of the Climate City Contract process in June 2023 and January 2024 are part of the first version of the Climate City Contract.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.facebook.com/gutesmorgenmuenster/

Table 60 4th KlimaTraining

Partner	Muenster
Event	4 th KlimaTraining
Date	06/03/2024 – 12/06/2024
Location	Muenster, Germany
Event website link	N/A

<p>Short description of the event</p>	<p>On the 6th of March 2024, the popular climate training course started for the fourth time. Participation was free of charge and did not require any previous knowledge. Until the 12th of June 2024, citizens worked in small groups to develop a personal roadmap on their way to a climate-friendly everyday life. Participants scrutinized the areas of mobility, housing, energy, consumption and nutrition and were accompanied by climate trainers. Mathilde Anneke Comprehensive School was already taking part with 25 pupils.</p>
<p>Abstract/publication related to the event</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Short description of the Abstract/publication</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Dissemination through social media</p>	<p>Press release, Facebook https://www.owl.jetzt/content/82764/2024-05-09-06-14-04-muenster-klimatraining-geht-ab-6-maerz-2024-in-die-4-runde.html https://www.dein-ms.de/klimatraining-geht-in-die-vierte-runde https://www.facebook.com/klima.muenster?locale=de_DE</p>

Source: Stadt Muenster/Philipp Berstermann

Table 61 Healthy Streets© Conference

Partner	Budapest
Event	Healthy Streets© Conference
Date	12/03/2024
Location	Budapest, Hungary
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	N/A
Short description of the event	The Hungarian Urban Planning Association and Urbavis organized a conference on March 12 th , 2024, with over 90 participants, aiming at sharing domestic and international best practices for the development of livable, walkable, healthy streets and urban centers.
Abstract/publication related to the event	Hatalmas érdeklődés az Egészséges utcák Konferencián (mut.hu)
Short description of the Abstract/publication	N/A
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 62 UP2030 Vision Workshop Thessaloniki

Partner	MDAT
Event	UP2030 Vision Workshop Thessaloniki
Date	12/03/2024
Location	Thessaloniki, Greece
Event website link	https://mdat.gr/2024/03/14/
Role in the event	Co organizer together with the Municipality of Thessaloniki
Short description of the event	<p>The invited participants to the workshop were municipal employees and elected vice mayors.</p> <p>The purposes of the workshop were to discuss with the participants the vision of the pilot area and the transmission of the area towards climate neutrality, resilience and just transition.</p> <p>The organizers presented, the findings of the on-site surveys showing a) the increase of the tourist services provision (tourist accommodation: hotels, hostels, Airbnb, etc.), b) the increased number of the closed businesses and consequently the empty ground floor shops, c) the occupation of public space by parked</p>

	<p>vehicles, and d) the lack of available green space the e) need for emissions reduction.</p> <p>Participants were divided into five groups; they were asked to envision the area in year 2030 and write down the headlines they would like to read in the "news of the day."</p>
<p>Dissemination through social media</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Source: Irene Tsakiridou</p>	

Table 63 UP2030 Vision Workshop Muenster

<p>Partner</p>	<p>BH</p>
<p>Event</p>	<p>Workshop on the development of a Pilot Vision for Muenster</p>
<p>Date</p>	<p>14/03/2024</p>
<p>Location</p>	<p>Muenster, Germany</p>
<p>Event website link</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Role in the event</p>	<p>Workshop Content Preparation, Speaker, Presentation</p>
<p>Short description of the event</p>	<p>During the Workshop on the Pilot Vision, Buro Happold together with the climate unit of Muenster and Fraunhofer IAO aimed to develop an overarching vision and guideline for climate-just district development.</p> <p>During the workshop Buro Happold presented their Climate Proofing Tool and the possibility for application in Münster. The workshop participants from the climate unit then discussed the challenges that currently exist in the work and how the Climate</p>

	<p>Proofing tool can be integrated into the City’s processes and structures. During the session, participants developed a vision for future cooperation, beginning with defining what a "climate-friendly city" means and its significance for their respective departments. This vision emphasized the importance of continuous development and maintaining a dynamic approach to planning and implementing climate-friendly initiatives.</p> <p>Within the workshop, Buro Happold and Fraunhofer together with Münster’s climate unit focused on ongoing processes and approaches already existing in the city, identifying barriers in mainstreaming these and defining needs of relevant stakeholders to ensure a more collaborative approach and climate-just urban development.</p> <p>The workshop outcomes include the further development of a Guideline that is intended to help integrate the topics of climate mitigation, climate adaptation and participation into all of the city’s projects in a holistic manner. Creating synergies between climate protection, climate adaptation, and participation was highlighted as a key objective.</p>
Dissemination through social media	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/up2030-he_up2030-urbanplanning</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/jill-theobald-5a3aa816a_up2030</p>

Table 64 Procura+ Conference

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Procura+ Conference
Date	14/03/2024
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	https://conference.procuraplus.org/study-visits
Role in the event	Co- organizer
Short description of the event	<p>The Procura+ Conference series (formerly EcoProcura) has been running for 25 years and is a dynamic and unique meeting place to exchange and equip participants with the latest professional information, advice and networking opportunities wanting to implement high-quality, cost-effective, sustainable, circular and innovative procurement practices.</p>
Dissemination through social media	https://m.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid

Lisboa

Highlights of heat adaptation work in 2023:

- As one of the 100 Mission Cities Climate Neutral and Smart by 2030, Lisbon reinforces its clear commitment by approving the Climate City Contract 2030 (to commit, invest and implement an adaptation strategy to cool the city).
- Gonalo Ribeiro Telles Urban Park was part of our efforts to “renature” the public space centred on people and climate-proof principles (along 6 hectares with more than 1000 trees planted, leisure, recreational areas, playgrounds, pedestrian and cycle paths were implemented).
- Several interventions involving the community and cooling the city were implemented <https://www.conexusnbs.com/>.

12

Ruas Verdes

Gonalo Ribeiro Telles Urban Park

Focus on heat adaptation for 2024:

- Reinforce interventions, commitments and investments to **reduce direct GHG emissions** by 80% (reference 2002) and redesign carbon neutral neighbourhoods
- **Synchronize climate adaptation policy**, to achieve climate neutrality by 2030, planting more than 200,000 trees (2019-2024)
- Map and monitor real time environment data, extreme temperature events and model the intensity of urban heat island
- **Increase water efficiency, reducing consumption**
- Promote improvements in Lisbon quality of life based on the ecosystem services.

C40 CITIES

Source: CML

Table 65 Workshop “Nature-Based Solutions – Climate Responses in Lisbon”

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Workshop “Nature-Based Solutions – Climate Responses in Lisbon”
Date	18/03/2024
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	N/A
Short description of the event	The objective of this workshop was to aim to delve deeper into the concept of Nature-Based Solutions and reflect on how science-based climate action can be led by municipalities and their citizens, enabling all – now and in the future – to thrive in balance with nature.
Dissemination through social media	It should be different sites: ANP/WWF no LinkedIn: As crises climática e de biodiversidade são emergências globais, mas a... Ambiente - Informações e Serviços (lisboa.pt) And then int the UP2030 folder Slides "Ação climática nas Cidades e SbN" (lisboa.pt)

Source: CML

Table 66 UDCW (Urban Design Climate Workshop)

Partner	UCCRN
Event	UDCW (Urban Design Climate Workshop)
Date	18/03/2024-24/03/2024
Location	Naples, Italy
Event website link	https://www.uccrn.education/napoli-udcw/
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	The UDCW focused on the district of San Giovanni a Teduccio, in the east suburb of the city. Selected students from each of the nine higher education institutions partnered with the project joined UDCW to develop a multi-disciplinary planning and design-oriented proposal aimed at supporting plans for a resilient district in Naples. The activities of the UDCW Naples represented an opportunity to implement UCCRN tools and apply them to a vulnerable urban context.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/uccrn-education_uccrn-udcw-urbandesign-activity-

Source: UCCRN

Table 67 2nd Visioning Workshop

Partner	LINKS
Event	2 nd Visioning Workshop
Date	20/03/2024
Location	Milan, Italy
Event website link	N/A

Role in the event	N/A
Short description of the event	<p>Each participant was introduced to set the stage for the day's activities. The primary objectives were to confirm the tool selected for the project, choose the specific area of focus, and identify the ecosystem services to be assessed. An overview of the project was provided, outlining its objectives and the actions planned to achieve them. This was followed by a presentation on the Ecosystem Services Assessment. The presentation emphasized UP2030's potential for urban development and sustainability, defining specific objectives aligned with Milan Municipality's goals. Tools and methodologies were identified for testing in ongoing processes, with pilot areas selected for implementation. An initial work plan outlined activity, timelines, internal team involvement, and engagement of external stakeholders. Key participants include the Urban Resilience and Urban Regeneration Departments, responsible for projects and planning, alongside the Green Sector and Air and Climate Unit of the Green and Environmental Department, and AMAT, the municipality's environmental agency.</p>
Dissemination through social media	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eleonora-esposito</p>

Source: Personal shot by LINKS Foundation

Table 68 Planet Festival 2024 in Alvalade

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Planet Festival 2024 in Alvalade
Date	23/03/2024
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	https://www.lisboa.pt/atualidade/noticias/detalhe/hora-do-planeta-celebrada-com-arraial/
Role in the event	N/A
Short description of the event	Pop-up/community event. On March 23rd, the Alvalade Market hosted the "Arraial Hora do Planeta". The initiative featured several sustainable workshops, games and workshops.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=1135267657705789 https://horadoplaneta.pt https://www.earthhour.org https://www.jf-alvalade.pt/arraial-da-hora-do-planeta-em-alvalade/ https://www.agendalx.pt/2024/03/21/chegou-a-hora-de-desligar-pelo-planeta/ https://pumpkin.pt/eventos/hora-do-planeta/ https://www.publico.pt/2024/02/21/azul/noticia/hora-planeta-hora-escuras-sustentabilidade-2081104 https://www.lisboa.pt/atualidade/noticias/detalhe/hora-do-planeta-celebrada-com-arraial https://horadoplaneta.pt/

Source: Credits: CML-DMCom

Table 69 Franco-German Future Center, Resonance Room on the Topic of Energy Sufficiency

Partner	Muenster
Event	Franco-German Future Center, Resonance Room on the Topic of Energy Sufficiency
Date	20/03/2024 - 21/03/2024

Location	Metz, France
Event website link	https://df-zukunftswerk.eu/aktuelles
Short description of the event	The Energy Sufficiency Working Group aims to raise awareness of the often-underutilized potential of sufficiency among political decision-makers in both countries. With the strategy for sustainable decisions that you are overseeing in Münster, you are contributing a valuable municipal perspective. In addition to Münster, the working group includes the cities of Freiburg (Germany), Lyon and Brest (France), as well as experts from IFEU, exciting thought leaders from science, business and civil society from both countries and representatives from the federal and state governments.
Abstract/publication related to the event	N/A
Short description of the Abstract/publication	N/A
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 70 UCCRN Expert Meeting - G20 side event

Partner	UCCRN
Event	UCCRN Expert Meeting - G20 side event
Date	27/03/2024
Location	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Event website link	https://uccrn.ei.columbia.edu/news/uccrn-climate-change-and-cities-expert-meeting
Role in the event	Organizer and Speaker
Short description of the event	UCCRN hosted a Rio G20 side event. In collaboration with the Columbia Global Center Rio de Janeiro, UCCRN Education, and UCCRN’s Latin American Hub, the Expert Meeting brought together international urban experts – as part of UCCRN’s Year of Climate Action – to engage in the global discourse on climate change and cities. The meeting stimulated breakthrough thinking, ignited opportunities for collaboration, and generated actionable strategies ahead of the upcoming G20 Summit, IPCC AR7’s Special Report on Cities, and Innovate4Cities.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:

Source: UCCRN

Table 71 UDCW Rio de Janeiro

Partner	TUD
Event	UDCW Rio de Janeiro
Date	25/3/2024 - 5/4/2024
Location	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Event website link	https://www.uccrn.education/rio-de-janeiro-6th-multiplier/
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	This workshop was the sixth UCCRN_edu Multiplier Event and consisted of UDCW sessions and panels with the participation of UCCRN_edu Associated Partners and local stakeholders. In this UDCW workshop students developed climate-resilient urban design scenarios for the neighborhood of São Cristóvão in Rio de Janeiro, grounded on scientific evidence and community priorities. During the final dissemination event, DELTARES presented their

	approach and tools for flood risk assessment and identification of risk reduction interventions that will be developed for the entire city and the neighborhood of São Cristóvão.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Source: Hugo López (TUD team)

Table 72 UCCRN_edu Multiplier Event Rio de Janeiro

Partner	DELTARES
Event	UCCRN_edu Multiplier Event Rio de Janeiro
Date	25/03/2024 -05/04/2024
Location	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Event website link	https://www.uccrn.education/rio-de-janeiro-6th-multiplier/
Role in the event	Speaker
Short description of the event	This workshop was the sixth UCCRN_edu Multiplier Event and consisted of Urban Design Climate Workshop (UDCW) sessions and panels with the participation of UCCRN_edu Associated Partners and local stakeholders. In this UDCW workshop students developed climate-resilient urban design scenarios for the neighborhood of São Cristóvão in Rio de Janeiro, grounded on scientific evidence and community priorities. During the final dissemination event, DELTARES presented their approach and

	tools for flood risk assessment and identification of risk reduction interventions that will be developed for the entire city and the neighborhood of São Cristóvão. The next steps will be taken with Rio Agua and the Flood control center.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/uccrn-education_uccrn-climate-change-and-cities-expert-meeting-activity

Table 73 UCCRN_edu Multiplier Event Rio de Janeiro

Partner	TUD
Event	UCCRN edu Multiplier Event Rio de Janeiro Rio
Date	25/3/2024 - 5/4/2024
Location	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Event website link	https://www.uccrn.education/rio-de-janeiro-6th-multiplier/
Role in the event	Liaison
Short description of the event	<p>The sixth UCCRN_edu Multiplier Event took place in Rio de Janeiro with a series of education, knowledge exchange, and dissemination activities, including UDCW sessions and panels with the participation of UCCRN_edu Associated Partners and local stakeholders. The Multiplier Event was hosted by the UCCRN_edu Associated Partners Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Rio de Janeiro and UCCRN Latin American Hub and served as an opportunity to test the replication potential of UCCRN_edu methods and tools in the Latin American context. The UDCW involved students from PUC-Rio, UNINA, and NYIT, who were called upon to develop climate-resilient urban design scenarios for the area of São Cristóvão grounded on scientific evidence and community priorities.</p> <p>This two-week workshop has been seen as a starting point for collaboration between the city of Rio de Janeiro and UP2030. We could seize the opportunity of this UDCW in São Cristóvão to share methods and approaches and initiate dialogue with the Rio's City Hall identifying areas of interest for the Rio pilot project and continuing collaboration in 2024 and 2025.</p>
Dissemination through social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/iamhugo_glad-to-have-been-part-of-the-uccrn-urban-activity

Source: Mateus Matos (external photographer)

Table 74 UCCRN_educ Multiplier Event Rio de Janeiro

Partner	UCCRN
Event	UCCRN_educ Multiplier Event Rio de Janeiro
Date	25/3/2024- 5/4/2024
Location	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Event website link	https://www.uccrn.education/rio-de-janeiro-6th-multiplier/
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	The sixth UCCRN_educ Multiplier Event took place in Rio de Janeiro with a series of education, knowledge exchange and dissemination activities, including UDCW sessions and panels with the participation of UCCRN_educ Associated Partners and local

	<p>stakeholders. The Multiplier Event was hosted by the UCCRN_edu Associated Partners Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Rio de Janeiro and UCCRN Latin American Hub and served as an opportunity to test the replication potential of UCCRN_edu methods and tools in the Latin American context. The UDCW involved students from PUC-Rio, UNINA and NYIT, who were called upon to develop climate-resilient urban design scenarios for the area of São Cristóvão grounded on scientific evidence and community priorities.</p>
<p>Dissemination through social media</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/uccrn-education_climatechange-climateresilient-urbanperspective-activity</p>

Source: UCCRN

Table 75 Community Event - Urban Art Collective Painting - Mural

Partner	Lisbon
Event	Community Event - Urban Art Collective Painting - Mural
Date	March, April 2024
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Short description of the event	Under the scope of the “Planet Festival 2024 in Alvalade”, a mural was painted on a municipal building under the motto “Small actions, big impacts”.
Dissemination through social media	https://www.facebook.com/reel/250481888141101 https://www.facebook.com/reel/6954897921304410

Table 76 Adaptive Pathways Workshop

Partner	Granollers
Event	Adaptive Pathways Workshop
Date	03/04/2024
Location	Granollers, Spain
Event website link	N/A
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	The workshop's purpose was to validate the objectives modeled on RESCCUE tool and Parametric Design Tool, developed by

	Aquatec and TSPA. Assistants of the session were the core group, all of them were internal stakeholders, and most had assisted in the previous sessions. TheBH Workshop was attended by 12 people in total.
Dissemination through social media	N/A
<p>Source: © 2024 Ajuntament de Granollers</p> <p>Gra</p>	

Table 77 6º Encontro UniverCidades 2024: Ideias para Lisboa, Centro de Informação Urbana de Lisboa (CIUL)

Partner	Lisbon
Event	6º Encontro UniverCidades 2024: Ideias para Lisboa, Centro de Informação Urbana de Lisboa (CIUL)
Date	11/04/2024
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	https://www.belasartes.ulisboa.pt/encontro-univercidades-ideias-para-lisboa-2/
Role in the event	Participant
Short description of the event	With an annual frequency, this meeting aims to publicize, in a dialogue-based manner, reference academic works on Lisbon, developed by students and researchers, based on strategic areas defined by the CML, in collaboration with partner Faculties and Institutes.
Dissemination through social media	N/A

Table 78 UP2030 Pilot Guided Visit (Alvalade Route)

Partner	Lisbon
Event	UP2030 Pilot Guided Visit (Alvalade Route)
Date	16/04/2024
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=16c65dd94f604f49ab5a17fc22e7841b
Role in the event	N/A
Short description of the event	A visit to Alvalade took place on April 16 th as part of the UP2030 project and aimed to make the Alvalade neighborhood and its dynamics (from social and environmental point of view) known, the four pilot areas selected and intervention proposals for each of them.
Dissemination through social media	https://m.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid

Source: CML

Table 79 Cultural diversity sessions

Partner	Granollers
Workshop	Cultural diversity sessions
Date	30/04/2024
Location	Granollers, Spain
Event website link (if applicable)	20240506_UP2030_Relat_2ndWS - eng (1).pdf
Role in the event	Organizer
Short description of the event	<p>Granollers, diversity sessions meeting were celebrated on Wednesday 30th of April 2024. The sessions' purpose was to get the opinion of the social and cultural diversity of Granollers. Assistants of the sessions were students from Centre for the standardization of the Catalan language and the Adult Training Centre, Centre Vallès 35 attendees in total (27 women and 8 men, between the ages of 17 and 70 years old).</p> <p>The methodology chosen to collect the opinion of these groups has been the Future Newspaper, and before this more practical workshop a presentation of the UP2030 project was made in plain and accessible language for all the people attending.</p> <p>All results obtained were included in Vision takeaways report.</p>
Dissemination through social media	N/A

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